

Towards
Natural
Language
Interfaces
in
Computational
Design

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Masterarbeit

Towards Natural Language Interfaces in Computational Design
Evaluating Large Language Models for Constraint-Based Functional
Layout Generation

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Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) show potential for making computational design accessible through natural language interfaces, but their capabilities for constraint-based architectural layout generation remain uncharacterized. This thesis develops and applies a systematic evaluation framework to assess whether current LLMs can generate functional architectural layouts that satisfy defined spatial constraints. The methodology comprises two components: a grid-based interaction method enabling LLMs to generate spatial layout information in text as response to text prompts, and a programmatic validation framework that evaluates constraint satisfaction across multiple single-space-level, multi-space-level, and global layout requirements. The framework implements topological analysis and methods from graph theory. It supports reproducible evaluation as well as adaptability for future research. The empirical investigation evaluates 19 LLMs on an office layout generation task for a 15×15 meter grid with 10 space types and 49 different spatial constraints. Results show that 16.1% of all layouts (48 of 298) satisfied all constraints, with performance concentrated in three models: OpenAI GPT-5.2 achieved 100% overall validity, Google Gemini 3 Pro 93.3%, and OpenAI GPT-5 80%, while sixteen others achieved 0–27% with the only at least partly successful Open Source model being z-ai GLM 4.7 at 27%. The analysis reveals a performance hierarchy by constraint scope: local properties show 75–98% satisfaction, pairwise relationships 63–88%, and network-wide requirements 52–77%. Violation pattern analysis identifies systematic clustering, with cascading failures when required spaces are missing from the generated layout. Findings demonstrate that LLMs can interpret natural language specifications and generate structured spatial configurations, but current capabilities show extreme performance variation between models and model generations as well as scope-dependent limitations. Network-level optimization of layout presents substantially greater difficulty than local property validation. Apart from this initial characterization of model capabilities the thesis proposes validation infrastructure for further research and deployment in LLM-driven design tools.

Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) zeigen Potenzial, computergestütztes Entwerfen durch natürlichsprachliche Schnittstellen zugänglicher zu machen, doch ihre Fähigkeiten zur constraint-basierten Generierung architektonischer Grundrisse sind bisher nicht systematisch untersucht. Diese Arbeit entwickelt und wendet ein systematisches Evaluationsframework an, um zu bewerten, ob aktuelle LLMs funktionale architektonische Grundrisse generieren können, die definierte räumliche Constraints erfüllen.

Die Methodik umfasst zwei Komponenten: eine rasterbasierte Interaktionsmethode, die es LLMs ermöglicht, räumliche Grundrissinformationen als Text in Reaktion auf Textprompts zu generieren, sowie ein programmatisches Validierungsframework, das die Constraint-Erfüllung über mehrere Anforderungen auf Einzelraum-, Mehrraumbeziehungs- und globaler Grundrissebene evaluiert. Das Framework implementiert topologische Analyse und Methoden aus der Graphentheorie. Es unterstützt reproduzierbare Evaluation sowie Anpassbarkeit für zukünftige Forschung. Die empirische Untersuchung evaluiert 19 LLMs anhand einer Bürogrundriss-Generierungsaufgabe für ein 15×15 -Meter-Raster mit 10 Raumtypen und 49 verschiedenen räumlichen Constraints. Die Ergebnisse zeigen, dass 16,1% aller Grundrisse (48 von 298) alle Constraints erfüllten, wobei die Leistung auf drei Modelle konzentriert war: OpenAI GPT-5.2 erreichte 100% Gesamtvalidität, Google Gemini 3 Pro 93,3% und OpenAI GPT-5 80%, während sechzehn andere 0–27% erreichten, wobei das einzige zumindest teilweise erfolgreiche Open-Source-Modell z-ai GLM 4.7 mit 27% war. Die Analyse zeigt eine Leistungshierarchie nach Constraint-Reichweite: lokale Eigenschaften zeigen 75–98% Erfüllung, paarweise Beziehungen 63–88% und netzwerkweite Anforderungen 52–77%. Die Analyse von Verletzungsmustern identifiziert systematische Clusterbildung mit kaskadenartigen Fehlern, wenn erforderliche Räume im generierten Grundriss fehlen.

Die Ergebnisse demonstrieren, dass LLMs natürlichsprachliche Spezifikationen interpretieren und strukturierte räumliche Konfigurationen generieren können, aktuelle Fähigkeiten jedoch extreme Leistungsvariation zwischen Modellen und Modellgenerationen sowie reichweitenabhängige Limitationen aufweisen. Netzwerkweite Optimierung von Grundrissen stellt eine wesentlich größere Schwierigkeit dar als die Validierung lokaler Eigenschaften. Neben dieser initialen Charakterisierung von Modellfähigkeiten schlägt die Arbeit Validierungsinfrastruktur für weitere Forschung und den Einsatz in LLM-gestützten Entwurfswerkzeugen vor.

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Introduction

1.1 The Challenge of Early-Stage Layout Planning

Early-stage architectural design begins with a program that specifies required spaces, their approximate sizes and relationships. In order to translate these requirements into a coherent spatial configuration, planners must satisfy multiple constraints: spatial sizing, adjacency, circulation and functional relationships.

Zawidzki et al. (2011) term this process as *functional layout generation* (FLG): creating graphic representations that establish sizes and adjacencies with approximate proportions as preliminary architectural plans. They frame this stage as a constraint satisfaction problem and implement algorithmic methods that encode domain knowledge explicitly as search constraints and validation rules. Computational design systems based on such algorithmic formalizations support design space exploration but require designers to express intentions in programming or mathematical logic. This translation introduces barriers for practitioners without coding expertise and limits adoption in early, iterative design phases.

Large Language Models (LLMs) suggest an alternative approach. LLMs interpret natural language, generate structured data and increasingly perform multi-constraint reasoning. If LLMs could translate programmatic requirements directly into spatial configurations that satisfy architectural constraints, they could make computational design accessible to those without programming or scripting knowledge.

This raises questions about how spatial relationships can be effectively described in language that LLMs can understand and generate and to what extent current models can produce functional layouts that meet those defined design requirements.

This research develops and applies methods to evaluate these capabilities.

1.2 Problem Statement

While AI image synthesis tools like DALLE-E Ramesh et al., 2021, Midjourney “Midjourney”, n.d. and Stable Diffusion Rombach et al., 2022 have transformed architectural visualization Huang and Haridis, 2025; C. Li et al., 2024; X. Li et al., 2024; Ploennigs and Berger, 2023, generative AI’s application to actual spatial planning remains largely unexplored. Most applications of AI in the domain of architecture focus on producing visual artifacts, concept images or rendering replacements, but do not translate design requirements into structured spatial configurations for downstream CAD or BIM workflows.

Traditional computational methods approach functional layout generation through algorithmic constraint solving Zawidzki et al., 2011. An LLM-based approach would contrastingly rely on learned spatial reasoning and text-based representations of space.

Although LLMs may appear to generate valid layouts or outputs in general, their outputs lack guarantees of constraint satisfaction or validity in general.

While recent work has explored LLM-based architectural layout generation, no established method systematically evaluates whether generated layouts satisfy defined architectural constraints. LLM capabilities for constraint-based spatial reasoning remain uncharacterized.

This thesis develops a grid-based communication format for LLM FLG, proposes an evaluation framework for constraint assessment and applies the framework to an initial study to characterize their performance.

1.3 Contributions

1.3.1 Methodological Contributions

LLM Functional Layout Generation Method A coordinate-based approach that enables LLMs to generate functional layouts through text-based interaction.

Constraint Validation Framework A programmatic evaluation system for the assessment of constraint adherence in grid-based layouts which supports reproducible evaluation across LLMs, constraint sets and building typologies through a flexible configuration system.

1.3.2 Empirical Contribution

Performance Characterization Across 19 LLMs Evaluation of models from Anthropic, OpenAI, Google and DeepSeek on office FLG on a 15m×15m grid with 10 space types and 49 design constraints.

1.4 Research Questions

Zawidzki et al. (2011) formalize functional layout generation as a constraint satisfaction problem. This research adopts their problem formulation to evaluate whether LLMs can solve the same class of problems without explicit algorithmic encoding.

Primary Question: To what extent can current LLMs generate architectural functional layouts that satisfy defined architectural constraints based on text input?

This question is addressed through three sub-questions:

Sub-Question 1: Which types of constraints show highest and lowest satisfaction rates across models?

Sub-Question 2: How do constraint satisfaction rates differ across LLM models varying in architecture, size and training approach?

Sub-Question 3: Do constraint violations cluster in specific patterns, indicating underlying reasoning limitations rather than random failures?

1.5 Scope and Limitations

This research develops evaluation methodology for LLM-generated functional layouts and characterizes current model capabilities through a 19-model assessment on office layouts.

What this thesis addresses Grid-based layout generation with discrete spatial units, single-turn generation establishing baseline capabilities, programmatic constraint satisfaction for early-stage design, and systematic evaluation across multiple LLM families.

What this thesis does not address Continuous geometry manipulation, multi-storey buildings with complex circulation, site-specific constraints and regulatory compliance, multi-turn iterative refinement or collaborative human-AI workflows.

The evaluation uses office layouts as a test case because their programmatic requirements are architecturally meaningful yet comprehensible without specialized domain knowledge. Whether findings generalize to other building typologies, grid dimensions or constraint sets requires further investigation. The framework's YAML-based configuration supports such extensions without code modification. Detailed methodological boundaries, design rationale and limitations are discussed in Chapter 3.

1.6 Thesis Outline

The remainder of the chapters is organized as follows:

Chapter 2 reviews literature on computational design tools in architecture, LLM applications in spatial reasoning and constraint satisfaction methodologies in design contexts.

Chapter 3 presents the experimental methodology, including the LLM interaction approach, constraint evaluation framework and validation metrics.

Chapter 4 reports constraint satisfaction performance across models and analyzes patterns in constraint types, behavior tendencies and failure modes.

Chapter 5 discusses the findings and their implications, addresses the research questions and examines what results reveal about LLM suitability for constraint-based design tasks.

Chapter 6 concludes by summarizing methodological and empirical contributions, acknowledging limitations and proposing directions for future research.

Literature Review

2.1 Functional Layout Generation as Design Problem

Early-stage architectural design translates programmatic requirements into spatial configurations. Architects receive specifications for required spaces, their approximate sizes and relationships, and must generate layouts that satisfy multiple competing constraints while allowing iteration and exploration of design alternatives.

Zawidzki et al. (2011) define *functional layout generation* (FLG) as creating graphic representations that establish sizes and adjacencies with approximate proportions. These representations serve as preliminary architectural plans, distinct from detailed design that specifies construction systems, materials or geometries. FLG operates at an abstraction level where spaces are represented as rectangular units on discrete grids, relationships are defined through adjacency and distance requirements, and validation focuses on constraint satisfaction rather than aesthetic or constructional criteria.

For the purposes of this thesis, the problem can be characterized by four primary constraint categories. *Spatial sizing constraints* specify required areas for each space, often expressed as ranges or minimum values that must be met within available area budgets. *Adjacency constraints* define which spaces must share boundaries to enable functional connections, for example, kitchens adjacent to dining areas, or bathrooms connected to bedrooms. *Circulation constraints* ensure accessibility by requiring paths between spaces and maintaining minimum clearances for movement. *Orientation constraints* specify relationships to environmental factors, such as living spaces facing south for daylight or avoiding north-facing bedrooms.

These constraints create a computationally complex problem (Baykan & Fox, 1997). The solution space grows exponentially with the number of spaces and available grid positions. A 15×15 grid with 10 spaces of varying sizes produces an astronomically large number of possible arrangements before considering constraint satisfaction. Constraints interact in non-obvious ways: satisfying adjacency requirements may violate circulation paths; optimizing space sizes may preclude desired orientations. When multiple constraints cannot be satisfied simultaneously, planners must prioritize, determining which requirements are essential versus negotiable. This prioritization typically emerges through iteration rather than complete formal specification, as conflicts often surface when attempting concrete configurations. No algorithmic procedure guarantees finding solutions efficiently, and when solutions exist, determining which best satisfies stakeholder priorities requires additional evaluation.

Zawidzki et al. (2011) formalize FLG as a constraint satisfaction problem (CSP), where variables represent spatial properties (position, dimensions, orientation), values are their possible assignments, and constraints are relationships that must hold between variables. This formalization enables application of CSP solution methods that systematically explore configuration space while eliminating invalid partial solutions (Baykan

& Fox, 1997).

More recent work maintains this constraint-based framing. Z. Li et al. (2024) frame space layout planning as optimization under multiple constraints in the schematic design stage. Liu et al. (2025) review layout generation methods across decades, finding that constraint satisfaction remains fundamental regardless of whether solutions employ rule-based systems, optimization algorithms, or learning-based approaches. Weber et al. (2022) categorize methods by strategy but emphasize that all must handle core constraint types, sizing, adjacency, circulation, that define valid architectural layouts.

FLG's formulation as CSP establishes it as a well-defined computational problem with clear inputs (space requirements, constraint specifications), outputs (spatial configurations), and validation criteria (constraint satisfaction rates). This formalization provides the foundation for evaluating whether alternative solution methods, including LLM-based approaches, can address the same problem space.

2.2 The Grid as Architectural Design Tool

The discrete grid referenced in FLG formulations for this work serves two functions: it is both a spatial organizing device used throughout architectural history and a data structure that enables computational manipulation. This duality enables the grid to connect design intent and algorithmic processing. The term *grid* refers to a spatial structure of intersecting lines creating regular cells that organize physical space, while *matrix* denotes the mathematical array of values in rows and columns used to represent and manipulate that structure computationally. When spatial grids are encoded as matrices, coordinate pairs provide unambiguous textual notation for positions, enabling operations that would be more complicated or impossible on continuous geometric representations.

Grid-based spatial organization has served architectural and urban planning since antiquity. Kostof (1991) traces the rectilinear grid from Hippodamian planning in ancient Greece through Roman centuriation, where “Romans commonly correlated the main north-south and east-west coordinates of the centuriation... with the cross-axes of the city.” The same geometric structure accommodates diverse programmatic requirements because, as Kostof argues, “city form is neutral until it is impressed with specific cultural intent.” Renaissance architects formalized modular relationships within buildings: Wittkower (1998) documents Palladio's use of proportional room ratios, square and a third, square and a half, square and two-thirds, and the double square, where spaces are sized as commensurate multiples of a base unit. This modular thinking anticipates the discrete cell allocation central to computational layout generation.

The Cartesian grid, orthogonal and uniformly spaced, has properties that make it

computationally tractable. Discrete positions create a finite state space rather than continuous geometric possibilities. Uniform cell sizes establish consistent adjacency relationships: each interior cell neighbors exactly four others. Direct coordinate addressing enables unambiguous reference to any position through row-column pairs (row;column). These properties distinguish the Cartesian grid from polar, triangular, or irregular tessellations that introduce variable adjacency patterns and complicate algorithmic operations. For functional layout generation, the 2D Cartesian grid abstracts floor plans to their essential spatial relationships without requiring the volumetric complexity of 3D representations.

March and Steadman (1974) establish the mathematical foundations for representing architectural space through discrete structures. Their treatment of “mappings and transformations” frames the architect’s drawing as a map with “one-to-one correspondence between the points in reality and their representation on the drawing.” Crucially, they demonstrate that spatial layouts can be encoded as graphs: “each functional space is mapped onto a point and if, when two spaces interconnect, a line is drawn between their representative points we produce a mapping known as a graph.” Adjacency requirements become edges; spatial configurations become graph structures amenable to mathematical analysis. This formalization parallels the constraint representation used in this thesis: spaces map to vertices, required connections become edges, and adjacency constraints specify which space pairs must share grid boundaries.

The grid’s capacity for textual representation through coordinate notation provides the foundation for the LLM-based approach developed in this thesis. Where traditional computational methods operate on numerical matrices through algorithmic procedures, language models process text. Grid coordinates translate spatial positions into token sequences that LLMs can interpret and generate.

2.3 Computational Approaches to Layout Generation

Given FLG’s formulation as a constraint satisfaction problem, researchers have developed algorithmic methods that search configuration space to generate valid layouts. These methods share a common structure: they encode design knowledge as explicit rules, represent spatial relationships through mathematical or symbolic formalisms, and employ search or optimization algorithms to find configurations that satisfy constraints.

Researchers have developed diverse algorithmic approaches to FLG: optimization methods that treat layout generation as maximizing objective functions (Zawidzki & Szklarski, 2020), evolutionary algorithms that explore solution spaces through iterative selection (Guo & Li, 2017), graph-based methods that embed adjacency requirements in geometric space (Grason, 1971), tree-based representations with adjacency-driven

fitness evaluation (Keshavarzi & Rahmani-Asl, 2021), rule-based systems using shape grammars (Stiny, 1980), and learning-based methods that train deep neural networks on floorplan datasets to generate layouts from graph-encoded constraints (Hu et al., 2020). Recent work attempts to reduce input complexity for learning-based methods: Xin et al. (2025) combine graph neural networks with agent-based modeling to generate layouts from “simple prompts” using training sets of only 150 samples, compared to the 60,000–200,000 required by comparable methods. Their hybrid approach generates topological relationships through GNNs and refines geometry through ABM, demonstrating that dedicated machine learning architectures can produce valid layouts with reduced training data. These methods successfully generate functional layouts across building typologies and enable systematic design exploration (Weber et al., 2022).

These methods share a common characteristic: translating design intentions into formal specifications before computation can proceed. This formalization requirement manifests concretely in how design knowledge must be encoded. Adjacency requirements like “kitchen adjacent to dining area with southern exposure” must become adjacency constraint matrices that specify which space pairs require shared boundaries, orientation vectors that encode directional preferences, and penalty weights for constraint violations. Optimization approaches require objective functions with numerical parameters: coefficients balancing competing criteria, threshold values defining acceptable performance, and fitness functions aggregating multiple objectives into scalar measures.

Parametric design systems, which integrate these algorithmic approaches into interactive environments, require designers to specify relationships through programming, visual scripting, or parameter definition (Caetano et al., 2020). Constraints become mathematical expressions, design intentions become coded algorithms or explicit rules, and exploration strategies become parameter configurations. This translation demands anticipating how formal specifications will behave computationally, a form of expertise distinct from architectural design knowledge.

The formalization requirement creates barriers when design requirements are ambiguous, contradictory, or exploratory. Architectural design is characterized as “a loosely structured, open-ended activity” (Zhuang et al., 2017), and early-stage design often involves qualitative priorities difficult to encode mathematically (N. C. Brown, 2020): how should “maximize daylight while maintaining privacy” be weighted numerically? When adjacency preferences conflict with orientation requirements, which constraint should dominate? Computational methods demand these decisions be made explicitly before generation begins, yet such prioritization often emerges through iterative exploration rather than upfront specification.

These computational methods successfully address well-defined layout problems

but share a common limitation: all require explicit formalization before computation proceeds. This formalization requirement creates accessibility barriers that limit adoption in practice.

2.4 Accessibility and Interface Challenges in Computational Design

The formalization barrier manifests in three ways: cognitive gaps between design thinking and algorithmic specification, extended learning curves for parametric tools, and organizational capacity constraints that limit adoption across the profession.

Parametric and algorithmic design tools involve programming logic and algorithmic thinking, skills that can be developed through hands-on exploration but require suitable training (Coates, 2010). Vazquez (2024) document the learning curve in parametric design education, where students must acquire both software literacy and algorithmic thinking skills simultaneously. Their incomplete recipe pedagogical strategy addresses the challenge of teaching students to construct algorithmic logic for design tasks, a skill distinct from traditional architectural training in spatial composition, material understanding, and constructional knowledge.

Beyond tool-specific skills, the cognitive gap between exploratory design thinking and formal specification is itself a barrier. Early-stage design involves ambiguous requirements, iterative refinement, and qualitative judgments (N. C. Brown, 2020; Zhuang et al., 2017). Anticipating how mathematical formulations will behave computationally, recognizing that “you cannot possibly know/predict the outcome without running the algorithm” (Coates, 2010) requires familiarity with algorithmic behavior distinct from the spatial and material reasoning central to architectural training.

Natural language offers an alternative interface paradigm that aligns more closely with how designers articulate requirements. Siddharth et al. (2022) review natural language processing applications in design, finding that NLP techniques support diverse design activities including concept generation, design space exploration, and requirements extraction. However, most applications focus on analyzing existing text (design documents, consumer feedback, technical publications) rather than generating spatial configurations from language specifications.

Recent work explores direct NLP integration with CAD systems. Kapsalis (2024) develop CADgpt, which integrates large language models with Rhino3D to enable 3D modeling through natural language commands. The system reduces learning curves for beginners who use intuitive language-based commands rather than menu navigation and parameter specification. Kapsalis (2024) emphasize democratization potential: natural language interfaces make sophisticated design tools accessible to

broader populations because they remove programming prerequisites.

Landay and Myers (2001) argue that more human-centered interface design requires interaction methods that match designers' natural working styles. Sketching interfaces and gesture-based input align better with design cognition than conventional software tools. For layout generation specifically, expressing requirements as natural language descriptions ("a kitchen adjacent to the dining area with southern exposure") corresponds more directly to architectural programming practice than encoding adjacency matrices, position variables, and orientation constraints in code.

The accessibility challenge affects not only individual skill requirements but also organizational contexts. Design practices vary in computational infrastructure, technical support, and staff expertise. Interface accessibility thus shapes not just individual adoption but patterns of access across the profession.

Natural language interfaces would address these barriers if LLMs can perform spatial reasoning and constraint satisfaction. Whether current models demonstrate such capabilities requires examination.

2.5 Language Models - Capabilities and Spatial Reasoning

Large Language Models (LLMs), neural networks trained on extensive text corpora to predict token sequences (T. Brown et al., 2020), demonstrate capabilities potentially relevant to functional layout generation.

LLMs generate structured outputs beyond prose, code, JSON, and domain-specific data formats, when prompted appropriately. Coordinates, dimensional specifications, and spatial relationships can be encoded as structured text that LLMs process and generate themselves. Multi-step reasoning, demonstrated through chain-of-thought prompting (Wei et al., 2022), enables decomposition of complex problems into sequential steps.

Penco et al. (2025) demonstrate that fine-tuned LLMs can translate natural language problem descriptions into formal constraint satisfaction models for product configuration tasks. Their framework generates MiniZinc constraint code, which a dedicated solver then executes. The LLM handles formalization by mapping language to formal specifications while constraint solving remains delegated to specialized algorithms. Kodnongbua et al. (2024) apply this pattern to architectural design, using GPT-4 in zero-shot mode to generate constraints and cost functions for mathematical program solvers that produce building schematics. Their sequential neuro-symbolic approach emulates traditional design stages, with LLMs handling constraint formalization while solvers execute spatial optimization. Together, these works establish that LLMs can

formalize design requirements for dedicated solvers but do not test whether LLMs can directly generate spatial configurations satisfying constraints without solver delegation.

Spatial reasoning capabilities vary across tasks and models. Yamada et al. (2024) evaluate GPT-3.5, GPT-4, and Llama2 on navigation tasks across different spatial structures (square grids, hexagonal grids, rings, trees) and find that models handle certain structures effectively while struggling with others, which suggests structure-dependent rather than general spatial understanding. Peng and Powers (2024) show that prompt design critically affects spatial task performance: on a 5×5 grid navigation task, providing relative location information after each step improved LLM success rates from approximately 15% to 68%. This sensitivity to how spatial information is encoded in prompts is directly relevant to layout generation, where constraint presentation may similarly determine model performance. Martorell (2025) extends these findings by comparing representation formats directly: Cartesian coordinate representations consistently yield higher success rates and path efficiency in grid-world navigation tasks, with performance scaling with model size. This result provides empirical justification for encoding spatial layouts through explicit coordinate notation. Wu et al. (2024) propose Visualization-of-Thought (VoT) prompting, where LLMs generate visual representations of their reasoning traces during 2D grid tasks including navigation and visual tiling. VoT improves spatial reasoning performance and outperforms multimodal models on these tasks, indicating that explicit spatial visualization within text-based reasoning enhances grid-based problem solving.

More comprehensive evaluations confirm partial spatial capabilities. Rizvi et al. (2024) develop benchmarks to characterize LLM spatial reasoning across topological, directional, and distance relationships. They find that while LLMs perform poorly compared to symbolic reasoning methods, performance improves with model scale, and fine-tuning yields gains of 7–32 absolute F1 points. GPT-4 outperforms open-source alternatives on topological understanding, the type of reasoning required for adjacency-based layout constraints. F. Li et al. (2024) identify a specific limitation: while GPT models show proficiency mapping natural language to spatial relations, they struggle with multi-hop reasoning where conclusions require combining multiple spatial statements. Chain-of-thought and tree-of-thought prompting strategies improve accuracy on multi-hop tasks.

Text-based spatial representation provides the interface between linguistic capabilities and geometric tasks. Leng et al. (2023) demonstrate that spatial layouts can be encoded as sequences for language model processing with Tell2Design, a dataset of over 80,000 floor plans with natural language descriptions. J. Li et al. (2024) implement ChatDesign, which uses pre-trained LLMs to generate floor plan designs from natural language through coordinate parameters. These implementations show that layouts can be represented as structured text that LLMs process and generate.

Galanos et al. (2023) demonstrate that fine-tuned language models can learn architectural layout generation. Their system, Architext, trains models ranging from 120 million to 6 billion parameters on a synthetic dataset of residential floor plans paired with natural language descriptions. The largest model (GPT-J) generates valid layouts at near 100% rate, with semantic accuracy between 25% and 84% depending on prompt complexity, broken down by constraint categories including room counts, adjacency requirements, and location constraints. These results establish that language models can acquire layout generation capabilities through fine-tuning on domain-specific data. However, Architext does not test whether general-purpose LLMs handle layout constraints without fine-tuning. Whether the spatial reasoning capabilities of zero-shot models extend to architectural constraint satisfaction remains an open question.

Makatura et al. (2023) find that LLMs excel at high-level reasoning but struggle with precise geometric computation, which suggests hybrid approaches where models handle constraint interpretation while algorithms validate geometry. Littlefair et al. (2025) test this directly for interior design: they find that LLMs cannot generate complete furniture layouts but can produce object lists and placement constraints when used in a structured workflow, with constrained optimization handling final spatial arrangement. Zong et al. (2025) demonstrate a similar pattern for floor plan generation: their system uses chain-of-thought prompting to guide LLMs in generating initial layouts, then employs diffusion models to refine outputs into final floor plans, explicitly noting that LLM-generated layouts “may lack precise geometric alignment and fine-grained structural details.” These hybrid approaches share a common architecture: LLMs handle high-level interpretation while dedicated systems handle spatial refinement.

These findings indicate that LLMs can process constraint relationships linguistically and formalize them as symbolic specifications (Kodnongbua et al., 2024; Littlefair et al., 2025; Penco et al., 2025), but their capacity to directly generate spatial configurations satisfying those constraints remains untested. Penco’s framework delegates solving to a constraint solver; spatial reasoning benchmarks show partial but inconsistent capabilities dependent on task structure and prompt design. Whether LLMs can both interpret architectural constraints and produce valid layouts without dedicated solvers is the question this thesis addresses.

Functional layout generation for architecture remains unexplored in LLM research. Existing work on floor plan generation incorporates constraints such as room types, adjacencies, and boundaries (Leng et al., 2023; J. Li et al., 2024), but these constraint formats require domain knowledge and preprocessing that limits accessibility. Jang et al. (2025), in a systematic review of 161 papers on generative AI in architectural design from 2014 to 2024, found that while 68.94% of AI applications focus on schematic design phases where layout generation occurs, image-based outputs domi-

nate at 68.32%, with only a single study successfully generating dimensionally accurate layouts by using graph neural networks combined with parametric modeling rather than language models. No studies systematically evaluate whether LLMs can generate grid-based layouts satisfying architectural constraints (adjacency, size, circulation, orientation) or characterize which constraint types these models handle reliably. The question of whether spatial reasoning capabilities demonstrated on navigation and simple geometric tasks transfer to architectural layout generation, with its complex, interacting constraints, remains open.

LLMs demonstrate relevant capabilities for functional layout generation: structured output generation, multi-step reasoning, constraint formalization, and partial spatial understanding. Whether these capabilities transfer to architectural layout generation, where multiple interacting constraints must be satisfied simultaneously on a spatial grid, remains untested.

2.6 AI Applications in Architectural Design

AI adoption in architectural design has concentrated on image generation. Jang et al. (2025) document this through systematic review of 161 papers from 2014 to 2024: applications focus on schematic design phases (68.94%), with images dominating both inputs (52.8%) and outputs (68.32%). Text-to-image synthesis models (DALL-E, Mid-journey, Stable Diffusion) enable rapid visual exploration but generate artifacts without dimensional specifications or parametric relationships required for CAD workflows (P. Li et al., 2024; Ploennigs & Berger, 2023, 2024; Ramesh et al., 2021; Rombach et al., 2022).

Jang et al. (2025) term this the “floorplan effect”: generated images appear similar to design drawings yet lack actual dimensions. Of 161 reviewed papers, only one successfully generated layouts with dimensional specifications, requiring integration of graph neural networks with parametric modeling. X. Li et al. (2024) confirm this limitation for text-to-image floor plan tools: outputs function as visualization aids that cannot inform downstream activities requiring structured geometric data.

Beyond image generation, machine learning addresses other architectural tasks: Zhang et al. (2024) apply generative adversarial networks to structural topology generation, while Huang and Haridis (2025) evaluate GPT-4o and Claude 3.5 on architectural synthesis. Both systems successfully generate individual components but fail to accurately assemble parts into correct spatial relationships, which indicates that current LLM capabilities do not extend to reliable constraint-based spatial configuration. Du et al. (2024) demonstrate that LLM-based multi-agent systems can generate BIM models from natural language, producing structured outputs with internal layouts and

semantic information. Their framework uses LLM agents to transform text into API calls, with rule-based model checkers validating outputs iteratively. This approach produces editable structured data rather than images, but relies on predefined domain knowledge for validation rather than testing LLM constraint satisfaction capabilities directly.

The concentration on image generation reflects AI's current strength in pattern recognition and synthesis, but creates a methodological gap for constraint-based design tasks. (Jang et al., 2025) found that variables representing design parameters account for only 18.01% of outputs in architectural AI research, with graphs and other structured formats similarly underrepresented. Tasks requiring dimensional accuracy, topological validation, or integration with Building Information Modeling systems remain underexplored because current approaches generate visual representations without the spatial relationships, dimensional specifications, or semantic data structures these workflows require. The later design phases (Design Development and Construction Documents), which demand such structured data, received attention in only 21.74% and 1.86% of reviewed studies respectively.

AI applications in architectural design have concentrated on visualization and optimization, not functional layout generation. Image synthesis tools enable rapid ideation but produce visual artifacts disconnected from design workflows. No current approach translates programmatic requirements into structured spatial configurations that satisfy architectural constraints. Evaluating whether LLMs can fill this gap requires methods suited to constraint-based spatial outputs rather than image quality.

2.7 Evaluation Methods for Generative Design Systems

Assessing generative design systems requires moving beyond subjective judgment to evaluation that quantifies performance, validates outputs, and characterizes capabilities. The challenge intensifies when systems produce spatial configurations: determining whether generated layouts satisfy architectural requirements demands validation methods that check constraint compliance, measure performance against design criteria, and identify failure modes reliably.

Computational design methods employ evaluation approaches that reflect their algorithmic nature. Optimization-based systems measure objective functions that combine weighted criteria for functionality, daylight exposure, view quality, and environmental factors (Zawidzki & Szklarski, 2020). Evolutionary algorithms iteratively refine solutions through selection and mutation, evaluating cost functions that aggregate constraint satisfaction and spatial quality measures (Guo & Li, 2017). Graph-based methods validate topological correctness before geometric embedding and check

that generated adjacency relationships match specified requirements (Grason, 1971). Jang et al. (2025) review evaluation methods across 161 studies of generative AI in architecture from 2014 to 2024 and find that comparative evaluation dominates (60.9%), supported by subjective assessment from authors (34.2%) or third parties.

Evaluating AI-generated layouts presents methodological challenges distinct from traditional algorithmic approaches. Jang et al. (2025) identified 105 unique evaluation metrics across 161 studies of generative AI in architectural design, with 25.5% of papers relying solely on visual interpretation or subjective assessment without formal metrics. Metrics borrowed from computer vision (Fréchet Inception Distance (FID), Structural Similarity Index (SSI), Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio) assess perceptual similarity between generated and reference images but do not address architectural considerations. Metrics from machine learning (precision, recall, intersection over union) evaluate object detection accuracy but do not validate spatial relationships or dimensional requirements. This fragmentation reflects a mismatch: evaluation methods developed for image quality or classification accuracy fail to address architectural requirements such as spatial usability, dimensional accuracy, and contextual specificity (Jang et al., 2025).

Constraint satisfaction requires programmatic validation that checks generated configurations against encoded requirements. Automated compliance checking systems validate BIM models through ontology-based methods and inference engines (Ma et al., 2024). Yet these validation approaches depend on translating requirements into computable rules, a prerequisite met by traditional constraint-based systems but problematic for systems that generate outputs through learned patterns or statistical inference.

Evaluation of LLM-based generative systems introduces additional complexity. Raju et al. (2024) address the challenge of domain-specific evaluation for LLMs and develop methods to construct evaluation sets that demonstrate separability across models of varying capabilities while aligning with domain requirements. Ege et al. (2024) benchmark AI performance on design tasks through controlled experiments where ChatGPT participated in a prototyping hackathon. The experiments demonstrate capabilities but also reveal limitations when real-world constraints apply. Lee et al. (2025) integrate formal verification techniques with LLMs for planning tasks and apply model checking to ensure generated plans satisfy specified constraints, an approach that improves reliability and user trust but requires formalizing requirements as verifiable properties. Ying and Sacks (2024) develop LLM-driven approaches for building compliance checking, where the model autonomously retrieves BIM data and executes validation procedures. For floor plan generation specifically, Yin et al. (2025) propose evaluation methods that incorporate professional architects' feedback alongside domain knowledge and train preference models on functionality, flow, and overall quality scores to align generated outputs with architectural standards. These

developments indicate that evaluating LLM-generated spatial configurations requires hybrid approaches: programmatic validation of constraint satisfaction combined with domain-specific assessment methods that capture design quality dimensions beyond rule compliance.

No evaluation framework exists for LLM-based functional layout generation as formulated in this thesis: grid-based spatial arrangements satisfying architectural constraints (sizing, adjacency, circulation, orientation) specified through natural language. Existing architectural AI evaluation focuses on image quality metrics for visualization tasks or qualitative assessment for conceptual design tools (Jang et al., 2025). Constraint-based layout systems evaluate through fitness functions specific to their algorithmic approaches (Zawidzki & Szklarski, 2020; Zawidzki et al., 2011). LLM evaluation methods address general reasoning capabilities or domain-specific tasks but not spatial configuration under architectural constraints.

2.8 Research Gap

Functional layout generation is a well-defined constraint satisfaction problem that computational methods address through explicit algorithmic procedures, all of which require translating design intentions into formal specifications before computation proceeds. This formalization requirement creates accessibility barriers, cognitive, educational, and organizational, that limit adoption, while natural language interaction potentially offers a closer match to how designers articulate spatial requirements.

Prior work establishes that LLMs can formalize constraints for external solvers (Kodnongbua et al., 2024; Littlefair et al., 2025; Penco et al., 2025) and that fine-tuned models can learn layout generation (Galanos et al., 2023). Hybrid approaches show that LLM-generated layouts require post-processing for geometric precision (Zong et al., 2025). Spatial reasoning benchmarks indicate partial capabilities on 2D grid tasks, with performance dependent on representation format (Martorell, 2025), prompt design (Peng & Powers, 2024; Wu et al., 2024), and limited by multi-hop reasoning demands (F. Li et al., 2024). No study tests whether general-purpose LLMs can directly generate grid-based layouts that satisfy architectural constraints like required sizing, adjacency and circulation without dedicated solvers or fine-tuning. No evaluation framework exists for characterizing which constraint types these models handle reliably.

This thesis addresses this gap. Chapter 3 develops an evaluation framework, communicates architectural constraints through natural language prompts, collects LLM-generated grid layouts, and validates constraint satisfaction programmatically, enabling empirical characterization of which constraint types current models handle and where they fail.

Methodology

Grid-Based Layout Generation & Evaluation Framework

This chapter describes the methodology for generating and evaluating LLM-produced spatial layouts on constraint-based design tasks. It covers the LLM interaction method, the constraint validation framework, and the statistical procedures used for comparison of evaluation results. The methodology is presented in general form and then applied to the office case study on a 15×15 grid.

3.1 Overview

The methodology integrates generation and evaluation. LLMs produce spatial layouts through coordinate-based prompts and structured JSON output (Section 3.2). A validation framework converts these outputs into topological models and evaluates eleven constraint types as binary pass/fail checks (Section 3.3). The constraints are configured through YAML configuration files which separates the evaluation logic from the constraint definitions. The office-specific instantiation is described in Section 3.4. Statistical methods for comparative analysis are presented in Section 3.5.

3.2 LLM Interaction

This section presents the approach for LLMs to generate structured spatial configurations through text-based interaction. The method addresses the representation challenge of communicating multidimensional spatial tasks to models operating on one-dimensional text sequences.

3.2.1 Grid Encoding

The method uses grid-based discretization with coordinate encoding for spatial reference. Spaces are represented as collections of grid cell coordinates (row;column format, e.g., "0;0", "7;3"), for unambiguous spatial communication without the need for visual processing capabilities. The coordinate system divides the layout area into discrete, uniform cells. Each cell occupies a defined area (e.g., 1×1 meter) and can be referenced through its row-column position. Spaces consist of one or more contiguous cells sharing edges, with contiguity enforced through the constraint that allocated cells within a space must form connected regions. This discrete representation transforms spatial design into a discrete allocation problem accessible to text-based models.

3.2.2 Structured Output

Models must produce responses conforming to a specified JSON schema with three primary components:

Reasoning Field: A brief textual explanation of design decisions, architectural principles and constraint satisfaction strategies.

Allocation Array: List of allocated spaces. Each space contains:

- Space identifier (e.g., “reception_1”)
- Name (e.g., “Reception”)
- Type classification (e.g., “reception”)
- List of cell coordinates representing spatial extent

Doors Array: List of door objects defining spatial connections. Each door specifies:

- Source and target space identifiers
- Specific cell coordinates on each side of shared boundary
- Architectural reasoning for connection

The schema provides structured data for automated topological validation and requires models to explicitly define spatial allocations and connections.

3.2.3 Prompt Architecture

The prompt communicates design requirements to LLMs through four components:

Role Assignment: Positions the model as an expert architectural designer responsible for creating spatial allocation plans.

Grid System Specification: Explains the coordinate system, cell dimensions and spatial extent with examples demonstrating coordinate usage.

Space Program Requirements: Lists required space types with quantities, providing the programmatic requirements the layout must satisfy.

Constraint Definitions: Specifies spatial relationships (connectivity, adjacency, avoidance) and other requirements (area allocations, access) the layout must fulfill.

The complete prompt is provided in Appendix A. The prompt structure was developed to communicate architectural requirements clearly while remaining agnostic to specific building programs. Different typologies require only modifications to the space program and constraint definitions.

```
{
  "reasoning": "Design strategy explanation...",
  "allocation": [
    {
      "space_id": "reception_1",
      "name": "Reception",
      "type": "reception",
      "cell_ids": ["11;0", "11;1", "12;0", "12;1"]
    },
    {
      "space_id": "kitchen_1",
      "name": "Kitchen",
      "type": "kitchen",
      "cell_ids": ["9;0", "9;1", "10;0", "10;1"]
    }
  ],
  "doors": [
    {
      "reasoning": "Connection justification...",
      "source_space_id": "reception_1",
      "target_space_id": "kitchen_1",
      "source_cell_id": "11;0",
      "target_cell_id": "10;0"
    }
  ]
}
```

Listing 1: JSON schema for LLM-generated layouts.

3.2.4 Generation Protocol

All models receive identical prompts and generate multiple independent layout attempts for statistical analysis. Generation follows a single-turn protocol: each model receives one prompt and produces a complete layout without iterative refinement or conversational guidance. This provides controlled experimental conditions for comparative evaluation. Responses that fail schema validation (Section 3.3.1) are excluded.

3.3 Constraint Validation Framework

This section presents the validation system for assessing architectural constraint adherence in grid-based layouts. The framework converts coordinate-based allocations into topological models for evaluation of spatial requirements.

3.3.1 Topological Analysis Pipeline

The framework uses *TopologicPy* Jabi, 2024 to convert coordinate allocations into topological models for constraint evaluation (Figure 3.1). It operates on text-based

configuration files that separate the evaluation logic from constraint definitions, therefore supporting different building programs without code modifications. The pipeline consists of three stages:

Schema Validation: Pydantic validation to ensure JSON structural correctness. Malformed responses are logged and excluded.

Topological Model Construction: Conversion of allocated cells into a topological representation. Grid cells become topological faces, contiguous cells merge into shells and spatial queries operate on a global connectivity graph. Figure 3.2 shows the topologicpy class hierarchy used for this conversion.

Constraint Evaluation: Eleven constraint types evaluate requirements and produce binary pass/fail results with diagnostic metadata identifying the affected spaces.

Figure 3.1
Schematic validation framework architecture.

Detailed descriptions for all constraint types are provided in Appendix C. Table 3.1 summarises the eleven constraint types across three categories.

3.3.2 Space Constraints

Contiguity validation uses connected component analysis on the cell adjacency graph to detect disconnected fragments (Figure 3.3). Width validation employs bridge detection in the dual graph to locate 1-cell-wide bottlenecks in circulation spaces (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.2
 Class hierarchy for topologicpy
 Note. From “Topologic” (n.d.).

Figure 3.3
 Contiguity validation via graph connectivity.

Figure 3.4
 Bridge detection for identifying 1-cell-wide bottlenecks in circulation spaces.

Table 3.1*Constraint validation methods across all eleven constraint types.*

Category	Constraint	Validation Method	Pass Condition	Fail Condition
Space	Count	Count matching spaces by type	Actual = required	Actual \neq required
	Area	Count faces in space shell	$\min \leq \text{actual} \leq \max$	actual < min or actual > max
	Contiguity	Graph connectivity check	Single connected component	Multiple components
	Shape	Rectangularity ratio	Ratio ≥ 0.8	Ratio < 0.8
	Facade (req.)	Geometric edge intersection	Space touches perimeter	No perimeter contact
	Facade (avoid)	Geometric edge intersection	No perimeter contact	Space touches perimeter
	Min Width	Bridge detection in dual graph	Zero bridges detected	Bridges present
Conn.	Adjacency	SharedEdges() between shells	ANY pair shares ≥ 1 edge	NO pairs share edges
	Door	SharedEdges() + door list	Each source has door to a target	Any source lacks door
	Avoidance	SharedEdges() negation	NO pairs share edges	ANY pair shares edges
	Global Conn.	Door graph traversal	All spaces reachable	Disconnected components
Layout	Grid Bounds	Metadata inspection for invalid cell IDs	Zero invalid cells	≥ 1 cell outside grid
	Cell Overlap	Build cell \rightarrow spaces mapping	Each cell in ≤ 1 space	Any cell in >1 space
	Total Alloc.	Count allocated cells vs. grid total	Allocated = target	Allocated \neq target

3.3.3 Connectivity Constraints

Adjacency, door, and avoidance constraints use edge detection to find edge-level contact between space shells (Figure 3.5). Global connectivity verifies that all spaces are reachable through the door graph.

Adjacency via SharedEdges()

Adjacency: PASS (shared edges > 0)

Figure 3.5

Adjacency validation using shared edge detection.

3.3.4 Layout Constraints

Grid bounds, cell overlap, and total allocation constraints operate on the layout as a whole rather than on individual spaces, verifying that all cells fall within the grid, no cell is assigned to multiple spaces, and the total allocation matches the grid size.

3.4 Office Layout Study Configuration

The methodology presented in Sections 3.2 and 3.3 is applied to an office layout generation case study. This section describes the case-specific parameters.

3.4.1 Grid and Program Specification

The study uses a 15×15 grid with 1-square-meter cells (225 m² total area). The grid dimension was selected to represent a tangible small office floor area while maintaining communicative clarity in the prompt.

The office program requires ten space types: Open Work Area, two Meeting Rooms, three Phone Booths, Kitchen, Lounge, separate Bathrooms (women/men), Storage, Reception and Circulation corridor (minimum 2-cell width).

```
- space_id: "meeting_room_1"
  name: "Meeting Room 1"
  type: "meeting"
  min_area: 0
```

Example space specification from configuration file (complete configuration in Appendix B).

3.4.2 Constraint Instantiation

The office configuration instantiates the framework's constraint system through specific requirements defined in the configuration file (detailed in Appendix B):

Space Requirements: Area allocations for ten space types, contiguity requirements, facade access for circulation.

Connectivity Requirements: Door connections between functional spaces and Circulation, required adjacency between Meeting Rooms and Open Work Area, Kitchen-Lounge door connection.

Layout Requirements: 225-cell total allocation, continuous connectivity throughout plan.

The configuration implements three types of spatial relationships, illustrated in Figure 3.6: door connections for mandatory direct access, adjacent relationships that require physical proximity without direct access and avoidance relationships that enforce spatial separation between incompatible functions.

connectivity:

- kitchen_1 door_to lounge_1
- bathroom_men_1 adjacent_to bathroom_women_1
- open_work_area_1 avoid bathroom_men_1

Three connectivity relationship types in YAML specification, corresponding to the modes shown in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6

Three connectivity modes in the spatial constraint framework.

3.4.3 Model Configuration

The study evaluates 19 Large Language Models from eight providers (Table 3.2). All samples are obtained through the OpenRouter API OpenRouter, 2025 with standardized parameters (temperature 1.0, top-p 0.9), generating approximately 15 layout attempts each. The data was collected between May 2025 and January 2026, with models evaluated as they became available through the API.

Table 3.2

Models evaluated in the experiment. Reasoning indicates support for extended thinking modes. Pricing per 1M tokens in USD via OpenRouter.

Provider	Model	Reasoning	Context	Release	In \$/1M	Out \$/1M
Anthropic	Claude Haiku 4.5	Yes	200K	2025-10	1.00	5.00
Anthropic	Claude Opus 4	Yes	200K	2025-05	15.00	75.00
Anthropic	Claude Sonnet 4	Yes	1M	2025-05	3.00	15.00
Anthropic	Claude Sonnet 4.5	Yes	1M	2025-09	3.00	15.00
DeepSeek	DeepSeek-V3 (0324)	Yes	164K	2025-03	0.19	0.87
DeepSeek	DeepSeek-R1 (0528)	Yes	164K	2025-05	0.40	1.75
Google	Gemini 2.5 Flash	Yes	1M	2025-06	0.30	2.50
Google	Gemini 2.5 Flash Lite	Yes	1M	2025-07	0.10	0.40
Google	Gemini 2.5 Pro	Yes	1M	2025-06	1.25	10.00
Google	Gemini 3 Flash (Preview)	Yes	1M	2025-12	0.50	3.00
Google	Gemini 3 Pro (Preview)	Yes	1M	2025-11	2.00	12.00
Meta	Llama 3.3 70B Instruct	No	128K	2024-12	Free	
Mistral	Devstral 2 (2512)	No	256K	2025-12	Free	
OpenAI	GPT-4o	No	128K	2024-05	2.50	10.00
OpenAI	GPT-5	Yes	400K	2025-08	1.25	10.00
OpenAI	GPT-5.2	Yes	400K	2025-12	1.75	14.00
OpenAI	o4-mini	Yes	200K	2025-04	1.10	4.40
TNG Tech	DeepSeek-R1T2 Chimera	Yes	164K	2025-07	Free	
Zhipu AI	GLM-4.7	Yes	203K	2025-12	0.40	1.50

3.4.4 Configuration Rationale

The 15×15 grid balances spatial complexity with prompt clarity. The office typology provides recognizable spatial relationships (meeting rooms near work areas, bathrooms separated from kitchen) that test diverse spatial reasoning capabilities. Space counts

and area allocations were specified to create a feasible but non-trivial allocation problem. Connectivity requirements test models' ability to maintain functional circulation paths and spatial adjacencies.

3.4.5 Design Decisions and Scope

Two methodological design decisions warrant explicit discussion. The coordinate-based grid encoding provides unambiguous spatial reference for text-based models, but alternative approaches (natural language spatial descriptions, graph-based encodings, symbolic spatial relations) may prove effective and warrant comparison. Similarly, the structured JSON output schema enables automated validation, but alternative formats (natural language with custom parsing, hybrid approaches) remain unexplored.

The constraint set reflects typical functional layout requirements but has not been validated by practicing architects or compared to professional standards. Performance metrics measure LLM adherence to our defined constraints, not architectural quality or professional acceptability. Results characterize model behavior within this evaluation framework rather than establishing architectural competence in absolute terms.

The methodology evaluates single-storey layouts on discrete grids. Multi-level buildings, complex geometries, site-specific constraints, structural requirements, MEP systems and regulatory compliance fall outside scope. Grid-based discretization limits representation of complex shapes, and findings are specific to the office program tested. Several uncontrolled factors may influence results: API version variations and context window differences across models, potential advantages for models exposed to discrete spatial data (e.g., game environments, ASCII art) in training, and the single-turn protocol (Section 3.2) excluding conversational refinement available in practical scenarios.

3.5 Statistical Methods

The validation pipeline produces constraint satisfaction results that require statistical analysis for reliable performance assessment. This section presents the statistical methods and hierarchical metrics used for comparative model evaluation.

3.5.1 Wilson Score Confidence Intervals

The framework uses Wilson Score confidence intervals for proportion metrics rather than Wald intervals, as Wilson intervals provide reliable coverage properties with small sample sizes ($n=15-23$ per model in this evaluation). For proportions near 0 or 1, Wald

intervals can produce impossible bounds (negative or greater than 1), while Wilson intervals remain bounded within [0,1]:

$$CI = \frac{p + \frac{z^2}{2n} \pm z \sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{n} + \frac{z^2}{4n^2}}}{1 + \frac{z^2}{n}} \quad (3.1)$$

where z is the critical value (1.96 for 95% confidence) and p is the observed proportion with sample size n .

This choice directly affects interpretability: a model achieving 0% validity with $n=15$ receives CI [0.0%, 20.4%], indicating that up to 20% validity cannot be ruled out given the sample size. Similarly, 100% validity (15/15) receives CI [79.6%, 100%]. These intervals inform the discussion of model capabilities in Chapter 5.

3.5.2 Hierarchical Metrics Structure

The framework implements hierarchical metrics aggregating from individual constraints → constraint-type-level (11 types) → overall layout validity. Individual constraints return binary pass/fail status. Constraint-type metrics aggregate through pass rates across all evaluated layouts. Layout validity requires all 49 individual constraints to pass (100% constraint satisfaction).

This hierarchical approach enables analysis at multiple granularities: overall model validity rates (how often a model produces fully valid layouts), constraint-type performance (which constraint types present consistent challenges), and individual violation patterns (specific failure modes).

3.5.3 Violation Pattern Analysis

The framework examines violation patterns through three analytical methods beyond basic pass/fail metrics:

Constraint Co-occurrence Analysis: Calculates Jaccard similarity coefficients between constraint violations to identify systematic dependencies. Perfect co-occurrence ($J=1.0$) indicates deterministic relationships, such as missing spaces causing cascading door connection failures.

Cascading Failure Quantification: Compares violation counts between layouts with complete space specification versus those missing required spaces, using t-tests to assess amplification effects.

Failure Pattern Categorization: Classifies invalid layouts by failure type (missing spaces, isolated connectivity failures, isolated allocation failures, multi-category

failures) to distinguish specification comprehension errors from optimization failures.

More implementation details are provided in Appendix C.

Results

Framework Validation and Performance Analysis

This chapter presents the results from the application of the evaluation framework described in Chapter 3 to the office layout example study. The framework processed 298 layout attempts from 19 LLMs out of 303 total generation attempts. Five layouts (1.7%) were excluded due to parsing failures or invalid JSON structure. Of the successfully parsed layouts, 48 (16.1%) satisfied all 49 constraints.

4.1 Overall Model Performance

4.1.1 Constraint Satisfaction Rates

The framework evaluated 14,602 individual constraint checks across 298 layouts, achieving an overall mean constraint satisfaction rate of 84.2% (12,299 passed). However, complete layout validity (all 49 constraints satisfied) was achieved by 48 layouts (16.1%, 95% CI [12.3%, 20.6%]).

OpenAI GPT-5.2 achieved a 100% valid layout rate (15/15 layouts, 95% CI [79.6%, 100%]). Google Gemini 3 Pro achieved 93.3% (14/15 layouts, 95% CI [70.2%, 98.8%]), and OpenAI GPT-5 achieved 80% (12/15 layouts, 95% CI [54.8%, 93.0%]). Additional models achieved partial success: GLM-4.7 (26.7%, 4/15), Gemini 3 Flash (11.1%, 2/18), and o4-Mini (4.3%, 1/23). The remaining 13 models produced no fully valid layouts. Table 4.1 shows the overall constraint satisfaction performance across models, ranked by layout validity.

4.2 Top Performer Analysis

Three models achieved validity rates substantially above others: GPT-5.2 (100%), Gemini 3 Pro (93.3%), and GPT-5 (80%). These results contrast with the remaining 16 models (0–27% validity). This section examines the failure patterns of these top performers.

4.2.1 GPT-5.2: Perfect Performance

GPT-5.2 achieved 100% validity (15/15 layouts), satisfying all 49 constraints across every attempt.

Table 4.1*Overall model performance on constraint satisfaction*

Model	Sample Size	Valid (%)	95% CI (%)	Pass Rate (%)
OpenAI GPT-5.2	15	100.0	[79.6, 100.0]	100.0
Google Gemini 3 Pro	15	93.3	[70.2, 98.8]	99.9
OpenAI GPT-5	15	80.0	[54.8, 93.0]	99.6
GLM-4.7	15	26.7	[10.9, 52.0]	92.4
Google Gemini 3 Flash	18	11.1	[3.1, 32.8]	92.9
OpenAI o4-Mini	23	4.3	[0.8, 21.0]	80.7
Anthropic Claude Opus 4	15	0.0	[0.0, 20.4]	89.0
Google Gemini 2.5 Pro	15	0.0	[0.0, 20.4]	91.3
Anthropic Claude Sonnet 4	15	0.0	[0.0, 20.4]	89.8
Anthropic Claude Sonnet 4.5	15	0.0	[0.0, 20.4]	80.8
Anthropic Claude Haiku 4.5	15	0.0	[0.0, 20.4]	76.2
Google Gemini 2.5 Flash	17	0.0	[0.0, 18.4]	84.8
Google Gemini 2.5 Flash Lite	16	0.0	[0.0, 19.4]	76.3
DeepSeek R1	15	0.0	[0.0, 20.4]	74.4
DeepSeek R1T2 Chimera	15	0.0	[0.0, 20.4]	75.6
DeepSeek Chat V3	15	0.0	[0.0, 20.4]	76.5
OpenAI GPT-4o	15	0.0	[0.0, 20.4]	73.5
Meta LLaMA 3.3 70B	15	0.0	[0.0, 20.4]	72.9
Mistral Devstral	15	0.0	[0.0, 20.4]	75.0

4.2.2 Gemini 3 Pro: Single Failure Analysis

Gemini 3 Pro achieved 93.3% validity (14/15 layouts), with one layout failing a single constraint. The failed layout satisfied 48/49 constraints (98.0% pass rate), violating the `min_width` constraint for the circulation space. Figure 4.1 shows the failed layout, where the circulation space contains a section narrower than the required 2-cell minimum width.

4.2.3 GPT-5: Failure Case Analysis

GPT-5 achieved 80% validity (12/15 layouts). Table 4.2 summarizes the three failure cases and their specific constraint violations.

Table 4.2*GPT-5 Failure Case Analysis*

Layout ID	Failures	Violation Type
4be3a649	2/49	Cell Overlap (4 overlapping cells) Layout allocation (229/225, 101.8%)
a5597449	1/49	Circulation width (4 bottlenecks)
ba430e44	1/49	Layout allocation (223/225 cells, 99.1%)

Figure 4.1

Gemini 3 Pro failure case: circulation space with a section below the minimum 2-cell width requirement.

The first failure (layout ID: 4be3a649) shows both `layout_integrity` and `layout_allocation` violations. Four grid cells at coordinates (8,12), (8,13), (9,12), and (9,13) were allocated to multiple spaces simultaneously, constituting overlapping cell assignments. The overlapping assignments resulted in over-allocation: 229 cells were assigned in a 225-cell grid (101.8% of target). Figure 4.2 shows the layout with overlapping cell regions.

The second failure (layout ID: a5597449) violated only the `width_circulation` constraint. The circulation space contained four single-cell-wide sections (bottlenecks), failing the minimum 2-cell width requirement. All other 48 constraints were satisfied (98.0% pass rate), including 100% space allocation and all connectivity requirements. Figure 4.3 shows the circulation space with bottleneck sections.

The third failure (layout ID: ba430e44) under-allocated by 2 cells, achieving only 223 of the required 225 cells (99.1% of target). This fell below the 100% allocation threshold required by the `layout_allocation` constraint. All connectivity and space-specific constraints were satisfied (48/49 pass, 98.0% pass rate). Two grid cells remained unassigned. Figure 4.4 shows the nearly-complete grid with two unallocated cells.

Figure 4.2

GPT-5 Failure Case 1: Layout integrity and allocation violations.

Figure 4.3

GPT-5 Failure Case 2: Circulation width violation with bottleneck sections.

Figure 4.4

GPT-5 Failure Case 3: Under-allocation with unassigned grid cells.

4.3 Constraint Performance Hierarchy

The top performers' failures showed 97-98% constraint satisfaction, violating only 1-2 constraints per layout. Performance varied by constraint type.

Figure 4.5 shows constraint satisfaction rates by type and model. Space-level constraints (presence, facade access, contiguity) formed a consistently high-performing band across nearly all models, while layout-level constraints (allocation, cell overlap) exhibited the widest variation, with several models scoring below 20%.

Table 4.3 ranks individual constraint types by pass rate. Three tiers emerged. The highest rates appeared among space and layout-boundary constraints: facade access (98.3%), presence (98.2%), contiguity (96.5%), and grid bounds (94.6%). Connectivity and width constraints fell in a mid-range: avoidance (88.1%), adjacency (78.7%), global connectivity (76.9%), and minimum width (75.3%). Layout-level constraints proved hardest: cell overlap (65.6%), door connectivity (62.7%), and allocation (52.2%). Allocation was the single most-failed constraint—fewer than half of all layouts achieved full grid utilization.

4.3.1 Constraint Co-occurrence

The co-occurrence analysis identified strong clustering patterns among constraint violations. Space count failures showed perfect co-occurrence (Jaccard similarity =

Figure 4.5
 Constraint satisfaction rates by constraint type and model. Values represent the percentage of layouts where each constraint type was fully satisfied.

Table 4.3
 Individual constraint satisfaction rates by constraint type

Constraint Type	Pass Rate (%)
Space facade access	98.3
Space presence	98.2
Space contiguity	96.5
Layout grid bounds	94.6
Connectivity avoidance	88.1
Connectivity adjacency	78.7
Connectivity global	76.9
Space min width	75.3
Layout cell overlap	65.6
Connectivity door	62.7
Layout allocation	52.2

1.0) with their corresponding door connection failures. Missing a required space type deterministically causes failures in all constraints requiring connections to that space. For example, layouts missing the lounge space (4 instances) failed the `door_lounge` constraint in all 4 cases, while layouts missing storage spaces (5 instances) consistently failed `door_storage` constraints.

Six constraint pairs exhibited perfect co-occurrence ($J=1.0$), showing systematic dependencies:

- Presence-presence pairs: `presence_phone_booth_2` and `presence_phone_booth_3` (14 co-failures), `presence_bathroom_men` and `presence_bathroom_women` (3 co-failures), `presence_meeting` and `presence_storage` (2 co-failures)
- Presence-facade pairs: `facade_circulation` failures perfectly co-occurred with `presence_circulation` (5 co-failures)
- Presence-contiguity pairs: `contiguity_bathroom_women` failures co-occurred perfectly with both bathroom presence constraints (3 co-failures each)

4.3.2 Cascading Failures

The sampled layouts were categorized by whether all required space types were present. Violation counts differed substantially between complete and incomplete layouts (Table 4.4).

Table 4.4

Constraint violations by layout completeness

Layout Category	n	Mean \pm SD	Median	Range
All required spaces present	276	6.8 \pm 5.1	6.5	0–17
Missing required spaces	22	19.5 \pm 9.6	19.0	6–44

Layouts with missing spaces showed a violation amplification factor of $2.9\times$ compared to complete layouts (19.5 vs. 6.8 mean violations). Each missing space eliminated the possibility of satisfying door connection constraints, adjacency requirements and global connectivity checks dependent on that space type.

4.4 Space Allocation Patterns

Beyond constraint pass rates, the framework captured space allocation patterns across models.

Overall Space Allocation Characteristics The framework analyzed space allocations across 10 space types from 298 layouts. Table 4.5 presents detailed allocation statistics by space type.

Table 4.5
Space allocation patterns by space type

Space Type	Mean	SD	Range	Samples
Open Work Area	55.8	29.3	7–210	304
Circulation	51.8	42.4	1–225	345
Lounge	16.7	10.3	2–66	299
Reception	12.6	8.4	3–46	296
Meeting Room	11.6	5.2	2–30	604
Kitchen	11.2	5.3	2–28	296
Storage	10.4	8.6	1–56	304
Bathroom (Women)	7.7	4.0	1–23	300
Bathroom (Men)	7.7	4.1	1–21	301
Phone Booth	3.2	1.5	1–15	869

Model-Specific Allocation Patterns Total cell allocation varied across models relative to the 225-cell grid target. Table 4.6 presents allocation statistics grouped by behavior.

Table 4.6
Total cell allocation per model (225-cell grid target)

Model	Mean	SD	Min	Max
GPT-5.2	225.0	0.0	225	225
Gemini 3 Pro	225.0	0.0	225	225
GPT-5	225.4	1.5	223	229
Gemini 3 Flash	224.9	1.3	221	228
Gemini 2.5 Pro	225.1	2.7	219	233
Claude Sonnet 4	224.9	3.5	214	231
Claude Opus 4	226.8	5.7	225	247
GLM-4.7	223.9	7.5	202	233
Claude Sonnet 4.5	216.7	8.0	201	226
Gemini 2.5 Flash	218.5	12.5	195	245
Claude Haiku 4.5	213.3	19.1	173	237
DeepSeek R1T2	234.8	28.8	169	305
Gemini 2.5 Flash Lite	212.0	29.9	166	272
o4-Mini	207.0	46.0	67	259
Devstral	252.9	55.8	173	352
DeepSeek R1	249.3	67.8	171	426
GPT-4o	94.4	35.2	56	203
LLaMA 3.3 70B	127.4	80.3	30	358
DeepSeek Chat V3	271.9	86.1	176	555

Four models allocated exactly or near-exactly 225 cells per layout ($SD \leq 2$): GPT-5.2, Gemini 3 Pro, GPT-5, and Gemini 3 Flash. These correspond to the models with the highest validity rates (Table 4.1).

GPT-4o allocated a mean of 94.4 cells (42% of the grid), with no layout exceeding 203 cells. LLaMA 3.3 70B showed similar under-allocation (mean 127.4 cells) with high variance (SD 80.3), ranging from 30 to 358 cells. At the other extreme, DeepSeek Chat V3 over-allocated on average (271.9 cells), with one layout assigning 555 cells, more than double the grid capacity, which directly indicates a failing cell overlap constraints.

4.4.1 Space Type Variability

The analysis revealed allocation the following variability across space types and models:

High Variability ($CV > 60\%$): Storage showed the highest variability (CV : 82.7%), followed by Circulation (CV : 81.9%), ranging from 1 to 225 cells. Reception (CV : 66.7%) and Lounge (CV : 61.7%) also showed substantial allocation variation.

Moderate Variability (CV : 50–60%): Bathroom Men (CV : 53.2%), Open Work Area (CV : 52.5%), and Bathroom Women (CV : 51.9%) showed moderate variability.

Lower Variability ($CV < 50\%$): Kitchen (CV : 47.3%), Phone Booth (CV : 46.9%), and Meeting Room (CV : 44.8%) showed the most consistent allocation patterns.

4.5 Representative Layout Examples

The following examples illustrate layout characteristics across the performance spectrum, from fully valid layouts to layouts with systematic constraint violations.

Fully Valid Example Figure 4.6 shows a layout from OpenAI GPT-5 (floor plan ID: 740e47d8-08e8-46d0-8634-81b3a858532e) that satisfied all 49 evaluated constraints. The constraint breakdown includes 27 passed space constraints, 18 passed connectivity constraints and 4 passed layout constraints.

Partially Valid Example Figure 4.7 shows a layout from Anthropic Claude Sonnet 4 (floor plan ID: 88ae997e-eca6-4130-bc4e-6e9892d416a1) that satisfied 48 of 49 constraints (98.0% pass rate). The constraint evaluation identified one failed constraint: `width_circulation`, where the Circulation space contained 5 bottleneck sections below the required 2-cell minimum width.

Figure 4.6

Fully valid layout with complete constraint satisfaction (OpenAI GPT-5).

Figure 4.7

Near-valid layout with single constraint violation (Anthropic Claude Sonnet 4).

Mid-Range Performance Examples Figure 4.8 shows a layout from OpenAI GPT-4o (floor plan ID: 8b0fda37-dbbe-4369-94cf-accc0cb3a631) that satisfied 28 of 49 constraints (57.1% pass rate). The layout exhibited multiple constraint violations: 3 space constraint failures, 10 connectivity constraint failures, and 1 layout constraint failure.

The space constraint failures included insufficient Phone Booth allocation (1 provided vs. 3 required), a fragmented Lounge space (2 disconnected parts), and circulation width violations (5 bottlenecks). The connectivity failures comprised 2 door connection violations (Kitchen-Circulation and Lounge-Circulation not adjacent) and 1 global connectivity failure (disconnected floor plan). The layout constraint failure resulted from under-allocation: only 101 of 225 required cells were allocated (44.9%), leaving 124 grid cells unused.

Figure 4.8

Mid-range performance layout with multiple constraint failures (OpenAI GPT-4o).

Figure 4.9 shows a layout from DeepSeek R1 (floor plan ID: 4aeaf7e4-b9b9-451b-97ef-d7686019d0dd) that satisfied 34 of 49 constraints (69.4% pass rate). The layout exhibited a distinctive failure pattern: missing 9 of 10 required non-circulation space types (Open Work Area, Meeting Room, Phone Booth, Kitchen, Lounge, both Bathrooms, Storage, and Reception), resulting in 24 space constraint failures. However, the model generated 15 distinct Circulation space instances, each violating the width constraint with 14 bottlenecks per instance. This resulted in total connectivity failure as the floor plan was entirely disconnected. The allocation constraint passed as the total matched

grid size.

Figure 4.9

Layout with only circulation spaces generated (DeepSeek R1).

Low Performance Examples Figure 4.10 shows a layout from DeepSeek Chat V3 (floor plan ID: 79f020fb-f9df-422d-a15e-3ffd44f66a4d) that satisfied 7 of 49 constraints (14.3% pass rate). The constraint evaluation identified 23 failures: 9 space constraint failures and 14 connectivity constraint failures. The space constraint failures included 6 missing required space types: Open Work Area, Meeting Room, Phone Booth, Kitchen, Lounge and Bathroom Women.

Figure 4.11 shows a layout from OpenAI o4-Mini (floor plan ID: 835fb630-c783-451e-a59a-e0b78756bdf1) that satisfied 24 of 49 constraints (49.0% pass rate). The layout passed 21 space constraints but failed 12 connectivity constraints and all layout constraints. The missing Circulation space resulted in 12 door connection constraint failures, as door constraints between Circulation and other spaces could not be evaluated.

4.6 Summary

The framework successfully processed 298 LLM-generated layouts across 19 models. The key findings include:

- Valid layout generation: 48/298 (16.1%) layouts satisfied all constraints

Figure 4.10

Low-performance layout with missing required space types (DeepSeek Chat V3).

Figure 4.11

Connectivity failures due to missing circulation space (OpenAI o4-Mini).

-
- OpenAI GPT-5.2: 100% valid layout rate (15/15)
 - Google Gemini 3 Pro: 93.3% valid layout rate (14/15)
 - OpenAI GPT-5: 80% valid layout rate (12/15)
 - GLM-4.7: 26.7% valid layout rate (4/15)
 - Additional models with valid outputs: Gemini 3 Flash (11.1%, 2/18), o4-Mini (4.3%, 1/23)
 - 13 models achieved 0% valid layout rate
 - Individual constraint pass rates ranged from 98.3% (Facade access) to 52.2% (Allocation)
 - Space allocation patterns analyzed across 10 space types from 298 layouts

Discussion

5.1 Introduction

Chapter 4 presented the evaluation of 298 layouts from 19 models against 49 constraints. This chapter interprets those findings, organized around the three research questions introduced in Chapter 1:

- **Primary RQ:** To what extent can current LLMs generate architectural functional layouts that satisfy defined constraints? (Section 5.2)
- **Sub-Q1:** Which constraint types show highest and lowest satisfaction rates? (Section 5.3)
- **Sub-Q2:** How do satisfaction rates differ across models? (Section 5.2)
- **Sub-Q3:** Do violations cluster in systematic patterns? (Section 5.4)

The sections that follow interpret these findings, situate them in prior research, and identify limitations.

5.2 Capability Threshold

The primary finding is not that LLMs generally struggle with constraint-based layout generation. Rather, three models demonstrate the task is feasible while sixteen others fail systematically.

Three models achieved validity rates exceeding 80%: GPT-5.2 achieved 100% (15 of 15 layouts), Gemini 3 Pro achieved 93.3% (14 of 15), and GPT-5 achieved 80% (12 of 15). All other models achieved 0–27% validity. As shown in Table 4.1 (Chapter 4), this boundary appears despite similar partial constraint satisfaction rates.

Overall, 48 of 298 layouts were valid (16.1%, 95% CI [12.3%, 20.6%]). Individual constraint satisfaction averaged 84.2%, yet complete validity remained at 16.1%. Models understand requirements and attempt and succeed in solving the task at least partly (relatively high individual constraint scores) but fail to consider every aspect of the task.

5.2.1 High-Performer Failure Modes

GPT-5.2 achieved zero failures across 15 attempts. Gemini 3 Pro had one failure (98% pass rate). GPT-5 had three failures. Each satisfied 95–98% of constraints. These are near-misses which showed 1–2 constraint violations per layout which were minimal geometric errors in otherwise correct designs. The specific failure cases are detailed in Section 4.2 (Chapter 4).

Lower-performing models show a different pattern. Widespread failures across multiple constraint types, missing required spaces entirely, and constraint pass rates of 20–40%. The three high-performing models show reliable multi-constraint adherence with occasional geometric errors, while the sixteen others show significant difficulty with constraint balancing.

5.2.2 Model Architecture Correlation

Four patterns characterize model variation:

1. Three models succeed, sixteen mostly failed. The partial constraint satisfaction rate overlaps, but overall validity separates them clearly.
2. GPT-5.2 (reasoning model) achieved 100% validity. GPT-5 (reasoning model) achieved 80%. GPT-4o (non-reasoning) achieved 0%. o4-Mini (reasoning model) achieved 4.3%. Gemini 3 Pro (reasoning) achieved 93.3%. Reasoning architecture clearly correlates with high performance in this task.
3. Sample sizes of $n=15-23$ per model produced wide confidence intervals for the overall pass rate (e.g., GPT-5.2: 79.6–100%, GPT-5: 54.8–93.0%). This prevents reliable ranking among lower-performing models. Though mean constraint satisfaction rates do differentiate these models (73–91%, Table 4.1).

Overall reasoning models expectedly performed superior to regular models. All models that succeeded in the majority of attempts are proprietary models and their detailed specifications (i.e., parameter count) are undisclosed.

All Open-Source LLMs except GLM-4.7 reliably fail under these specific experimental conditions. Three models (GPT-5.2, Gemini 3 Pro, GPT-5) cross the viability threshold and perform reliably well.

5.3 Constraint Scope Gradient

The results demonstrate model performance that follows a hierarchy based on the scope of constraints, as shown in Table 4.3 (Chapter 4). Local single-space properties achieve the highest satisfaction: facade access (98.3%), presence (98.2%), contiguity (96.5%), with minimum width lower at 75.3%.

Pairwise relationships show intermediate performance: avoidance (88.1%), adjacency (78.7%), door connections (62.7%).

Network-wide requirements perform worst: global connectivity (76.9%), allocation (52.2%).

This scope gradient suggests models handle single-space properties more reliably than relational constraints. Local constraints require verification of properties of individual spaces (contiguity, boundary position). Pairwise constraints require coordinating two spaces which is a higher level of complexity. Network-wide constraints which ensure that all spaces connect through doors (62.7%) or fill up the entire grid (52.2%) require placement of spatial elements and apertures across the entire layout.

Door connections (62.7%) present a special case: despite being a pairwise constraint, they perform worse than global connectivity (76.9%). This may reflect the specificity of the requirement. Valid door connections require placement at shared boundaries between two adjacent spaces which combines placing the two required spaces next to each other, identifying where they meet and specifying one cell on each side of their border. The door constraint logically fits into the group of pairwise constraints but is more complex and requires more steps to pass.

Several hypotheses could explain the overall scope gradient: sequential generation challenges (early decisions constrain later options), working memory limitations (tracking many interdependencies), or attention mechanism locality (local context vs. global state). These cannot be tested without analyzing model internals.

5.4 Failure Patterns

Constraint violations show clustering with cascading failure patterns.

Layouts with all required spaces present showed 6.8 ± 5.1 violations (mean \pm SD). Layouts missing required spaces showed 19.5 ± 9.6 violations which is a $2.9\times$ amplification (see Section 4.3, Chapter 4). Missing a space eliminates the possibility of satisfying all constraints that are reliant on that specific space. A single specification error propagates to 3–5 dependent constraints.

5.4.1 Co-occurrence Patterns

Six constraint pairs showed Jaccard similarity = 1.0 (perfect correlation). Presence failures perfectly predicted related contiguity and facade access failures. Table 5.1 shows examples.

As described the correlating failures within a single space that contain a presence violation are inherent to the design of the constraint system. If there is no women's restroom this room logically cannot consist of contiguous cells.

Table 5.1*Perfect co-occurrence pairs (Jaccard similarity = 1.0)*

Constraint A	Constraint B	Co-failures
presence_phone_booth_2	presence_phone_booth_3	14
facade_circulation	presence_circulation	5
contiguity_bathroom_women	presence_bathroom_women	3
contiguity_bathroom_women	presence_bathroom_men	3
presence_bathroom_men	presence_bathroom_women	3
presence_meeting	presence_storage	2

5.4.2 Model-Specific Patterns

The list below as well as the constraint heatmap (Figure 4.5) visualizes model-specific failure profiles:

Claude Opus 4, Sonnet 4, Gemini 2.5 Pro Near-universal presence satisfaction (100%) with low scores on connectivity constraints (door, adjacency) and min_width. These models generate required spaces correctly but struggle with relational positioning.

GPT-4o, Llama 3.3 70B 0% on allocation and global connectivity, with low door satisfaction. Failures span multiple constraint types.

DeepSeek variants, Gemini Flash Lite Low scores across allocation, cell overlap, and connectivity constraints. Broad failure profiles across most constraint types.

GPT-5.2, Gemini 3 Pro, GPT-5 Minimal or no failures. GPT-5.2 achieved zero failures. Gemini 3 Pro’s single failure was a min_width violation. GPT-5’s three failures involved allocation, cell overlap, and min_width constraints.

5.4.3 Interpretation

The clustering suggests three distinct failure types that require different solutions. Specification comprehension failures i.e. missing required spaces could reflect problems in comprehension of the full instruction which could be addressable through clearer prompting and stronger emphasis on the identified problematic parts of the task. The lack of required spaces was rare (presence satisfaction exceeds 98%) but cascades into dependent constraint failures (Section 4.3).

Inability to allocate all 225 grid cells and ‘forgetting’ that a cell has already been allocated to a space manifest as low allocation (52.2%) and cell overlap (65.6%) satisfaction and reflect multi-objective problems addressable likely attributable to difficulties in attention over many similar tokens within the JSON response schema.

Relational multi-step execution failures, the inability to reliably achieve connectivity patterns, manifest as low door (62.7%) and global connectivity (76.9%) satisfaction and reflect network-level coordination problems that may require fundamentally different approaches.

5.5 Practical Implications

5.5.1 Validation Infrastructure is Mandatory, Not Optional

250 of 298 layouts contained constraint violations. LLM layout generation cannot be deployed without programmatic validation.

Practitioners cannot manually verify 49 constraints per layout. Visual inspection misses violations; even near-miss failures from high-performing models passed 95–98% of constraints but were still invalid. Without validation, unreliable outputs undermine trust and usability.

The framework enables automated constraint checking and diagnostic feedback for iterative refinement. For robust LLM-based workflows the required workflow would be:

```
User Input → LLM Generation → Validation Framework → {Valid:  
Use | Invalid: Iterate}
```

The programmatic validation step is essential for reliable output.

5.5.2 Natural Language Specification: Technical Feasibility Established

Validation infrastructure addresses the LLM reliability challenge. How to ensure generated layouts are correct. But this assumes the generation approach itself has merit. Does natural language specification offer genuine advantages over parametric tools?

LLMs can interpret architectural constraints expressed in natural language and generate structured layouts. High individual constraint satisfaction (contiguity 96.5%, presence 98.2%) shows reliable comprehension: models understand space types, size requirements and contiguity needs. Structured JSON output enables programmatic processing which additionally allows for conversion into widely-used data formats for geometry (e.g. BREP).

At this stage this does not prove improvement of user experience over parametric or algorithmic tools nor gained accessibility. This requires implementation of a user interface and comprehensive user studies.

For the validation to work formalization is still required but relocated. Requirements or constraint configurations are expressed in a simple text-based file format (YAML).

Specifying those configurations in actual natural language was not part of the experiment. Instructing an LLM to translate an utterance about requirements to this YAML format in itself is trivial though definition and evaluation of the response is not.

5.6 Situating in Prior Research

5.6.1 Extension of LLM Spatial Reasoning Research

Prior work identified multi-step and structure-dependent limitations in abstract spatial reasoning tasks. The findings from the conducted experiments aim to extend those patterns to architectural layout generation.

Peng and Powers (2024) studied multi-step spatial transformations. Their task involved relative positioning with coordinate transformations. They found that prompt design critically affects performance, with relative location information improving success from 15% to 68%. This evaluation similarly found that constraint scope affects satisfaction rates (local 95–98%, network-wide 52–77%). The alignment: spatial reasoning performance depends on how information is structured and presented, not just task difficulty.

Yamada et al. (2024) examined structure-dependent spatial understanding. Their task involved navigation through different graph structures (grids, rings, trees). Performance varied by structure type. This evaluation found performance varied by constraint scope (local 71–98%, network 52–77%). The alignment: structure-dependency extends to architectural generation. The extension: constraint scope (local vs. network) matters more than constraint type.

Rizvi et al. (2024) benchmarked spatial reasoning capabilities (topological, directional, distance). They found poor baseline performance with substantial improvement from scale and fine-tuning. This evaluation found related spatial reasoning succeeds: adjacency constraints (78.7%) and contiguity constraints (96.5%) involve spatial relationships analogous to Rizvi’s topological category. The alignment: topological relationships are accessible to LLMs. The extension: network-level topological reasoning shows moderate success (global connectivity 76.9%).

Prior work identified multi-step and structure-dependent limitations in abstract tasks. These findings confirm these patterns extend to architectural layout generation, with constraint scope as the key variable.

5.6.2 Relationship to Constraint Satisfaction Problem Formalization

Zawidzki et al. (2011) framed functional layout generation as a constraint satisfaction problem. The CSP formulation was adopted as a reference. This work does not claim LLMs solve CSPs algorithmically.

There is a key distinction: CSP solvers use systematic search with constraint propagation, provide completeness guarantees and operate deterministically. LLMs use probabilistic generation through learned patterns, produce indeterministic outputs without completeness guarantees.

5.6.3 Complementary Pattern to Floorplan Effect

Jang et al. (2025) documented the “floorplan effect” in image-based generative AI. They found that image-based models produce visually plausible layouts but lacking dimensional accuracy. As their strength they identify visual coherence and aesthetic patterns. As a weakness of this approach the authors criticize that from images no direct downstream adaptation or modification can be performed.

The method developed for this thesis instead produces dimensionally precise layouts with variable constraint satisfaction. The designs generated by the models are stored in a simple, parsable JSON format and can easily be exported to any open 3D format.

Still both approaches, image generation and text generation, show the same issue. AI generation lacks guarantees of validity. This implies that validation infrastructure is essential regardless of generation modality. The proposed framework addresses the identified validation gap. It enables assessment of dimensional accuracy and constraint satisfaction. It applies to image-based outputs, if converted to coordinates, and text-based outputs.

5.6.4 Addressing Evaluation Fragmentation in Architectural AI

Jang et al. (2025) documented evaluation fragmentation: 105 unique metrics across 161 AI-in-architecture studies, 25.5% relying solely on subjective assessment, computer vision metrics measuring perceptual similarity rather than architectural validity. They called for methods assessing dimensional accuracy and constraint satisfaction.

Instead of relying on borrowed metrics from other fields, this thesis contributes a framework for programmatic constraint evaluation with hierarchical metrics (individual constraints → constraint categories → overall validity), adaptability for different building typologies and diagnostic feedback identifying specific violations.

In that sense the constraints themselves can be seen as metrics. For future work it

would be helpful to develop an ontology for the constraint set used by the framework which helps in defining, describing and extending them.

5.7 Limitations and Interpretive Boundaries

This section distinguishes established findings from unsupported claims.

5.7.1 Claims Not Supported by Findings

“Fundamental limitations” in LLM spatial reasoning Instead it was demonstrated that moderate overall performance on global connectivity (76.9%) under single-turn, grid-based, office layout conditions. What cannot be claimed: this reflects fundamental architectural limitation vs. methodological artifact. Why not: tested one representation, one prompt structure, one task type. Needed: alternative representations (graph-based, continuous geometry), prompt variations, diverse typologies.

“Natural language interfaces improve accessibility.” What was demonstrated: technical feasibility (LLMs interpret NL constraints and generate structured outputs). What cannot be claimed: users find this easier than parametric tools. Why not: no user studies, no task completion comparisons, no learning curve measurements. Needed: comparative UX studies with architects of varying computational experience.

“Performance hierarchy reflects attention locality / training data / working memory.” What was demonstrated: behavioral pattern (performance degrades with constraint scope). A definitive explanation for why this occurs cannot be given based on the findings for lack of access to model internals.

“Iterative refinement will recover near-miss failures.” What was demonstrated: high-performer failures satisfy 95–98% of constraints. The validation framework produces diagnostic feedback. What cannot be claimed: iterative refinement improves validity, converges reliably, or works for lower-performing models. Why not: have not implemented or tested multi-turn refinement. Needed: implement iterative loop, evaluate convergence and validity improvement (Chapter 6).

“Constraint satisfaction predicts architectural quality.” What was demonstrated: LLMs satisfy the defined constraints at varying rates. What cannot be claimed: valid layouts are architecturally acceptable to practitioners. Why not: constraints not validated by practicing architects; no expert review of outputs. Needed: expert evaluation study (Section 5.7.2).

5.7.2 Circular Reasoning Problem

One limitation affects all interpretations:

1. 49 constraints were defined to evaluate LLM capability
2. LLM performance was measured against these constraints
3. LLM capability gaps were concluded based on constraint satisfaction rates

But the configuration of constraints itself is an unvalidated assumption and not validated by practitioners. The configuration may be unrealistic, contradictory, or over-specified. They may not predict architectural quality or professional acceptability.

What this means for interpretation: As long as the constraint design is unvalidated, all performance claims are primarily bound to constraint adherence per se and not to architectural capabilities.

This changes interpretation of LLM capability gaps and determines whether the framework measures something architecturally meaningful.

Future work regarding this problem is detailed in Chapter 6.

5.7.3 Generalization Boundaries

The findings characterize performance under very specific conditions.

Tested configuration: single-turn generation, grid-based representation (15×15, 1m² cells), forced JSON response, office building typology, specific set of constraints, standard sampling parameters (temperature=1.0, top-p=0.9).

Untested variations: multi-turn interaction with feedback, alternative spatial representations (text grid, chessboard notation, natural language), different building types (residential, healthcare, educational), larger/smaller grids (complexity scaling), different constraint sets (regulatory codes, accessibility standards, structural), few-shot examples or alternative prompt structures, different sampling parameters.

Findings cannot be claimed to generalize beyond the tested conditions.

Furthermore the sample size per model (15–23) is relatively small. For more reliable results larger sample sizes would be required.

The findings should be treated as initial characterization, not definitive assessment of LLM capabilities for architecture.

5.8 Summary

Three models cross a capability threshold (GPT-5.2: 100%, Gemini 3 Pro: 93.3%, GPT-5: 80%) while sixteen others achieve 0–27% validity. Performance follows a

scope gradient: local constraints (75–98%) outperform network-wide requirements (52–77%), and violations cluster through cascading failures and model-specific patterns (Section 5.4).

All claims about architectural capabilities are conditional on the unvalidated constraint set (Section 5.7.2) and bound to this specific limited experimental setup.

Conclusion

6.1 Summary of Findings

This thesis evaluated whether current large language models can generate architectural functional layouts that satisfy defined constraints. The evaluation tested 19 models on a grid-based office layout task with 49 constraints across local space-level, space-pair-level, and global connectivity categories.

Three models crossed a capability threshold: GPT-5.2 achieved 100% validity (15 of 15 layouts), Gemini 3 Pro achieved 93.3% (14 of 15), and GPT-5 achieved 80% (12 of 15). Sixteen other models achieved 0–27% validity. Overall, 48 of 298 layouts were valid (16.1%), while individual constraint satisfaction averaged 84.2%.

Performance followed a scope gradient: local constraints achieved highest satisfaction (presence 98.2%, contiguity 96.5%), pairwise relationships showed intermediate performance (adjacency 78.7%), and network-wide requirements performed worst (global connectivity 76.9%, complete allocation 52.2%). Violations clustered systematically through cascading failures rather than random distributions.

All findings are conditional on the unvalidated constraint set and bounded to this experimental configuration of a grid-based, single-turn, office layout generation.

6.2 Contribution

The primary contribution is empirical: frontier large language models demonstrate spatial reasoning capability sufficient for constraint-based functional layout generation at the complexity level tested. Capabilities are not universal. 16 out of 19 models failed systematically to generate a layout adhering to all defined constraints but the three high-performing models show that the task is feasible for current language models. This finding shifts the question from “Can LLMs generate valid layouts?” to “How can this capability be more deeply understood, extended and applied in practice?” The demonstrated feasibility motivates exploration of more complex design scenarios, richer constraint vocabularies, and practical interfaces for architectural practice.

The developed validation framework provides infrastructure for this exploration: programmatic constraint checking, diagnostic feedback generation, and reproducible evaluation across models and configurations.

6.3 Future Research Directions

The demonstrated capability motivates research directions that would be speculative without evidence of baseline feasibility. This section organizes future work from methodological refinements to application-oriented extensions.

6.3.1 Methodological Refinements

Iterative Refinement Through Diagnostic Feedback

Single-turn generation yields 16.1% overall validity. The validation framework produces diagnostic output identifying specific constraint violations per layout. These two facts create the infrastructure for a generate–validate–iterate loop in which the LLM receives violation feedback and regenerates.

When high-performing models fail, they satisfy often times still pass a high percentage of constraints. Automated targeted feedback fed back to the models could enable them to recover and correct mistakes from a previous attempt. Violations cascade from upstream errors: layouts missing required spaces showed $2.9\times$ more violations than complete layouts. Correcting a root cause would resolve multiple dependent violations simultaneously.

Figure 6.1

Proposed iterative refinement loop: LLM generation with validation feedback

The proposed loop (Figure 6.1): the user provides requirements, the LLM generates a layout, the validation framework evaluates constraints and returns violation diagnostics, if violations exist, diagnostics are provided to the LLM for regeneration. The cycle repeats until valid or a maximum iteration count is reached.

An alternative variant allocates one space at a time (Figure 6.2), reducing the coordination burden per inference step. Network-wide constraints (52–77% satisfaction)

represent the weakest category; sequential placement may allow local consistency while building toward global satisfaction incrementally. This approach would require more total inference steps but each step would be simpler though the option to edit already allocated or re-place spaces would be needed.

Figure 6.2

Alternative iterative approach: single-space allocation with validation feedback

Prompt Engineering and Representation

The evaluation used a single prompt structure and grid encoding. Systematic variation could reveal whether performance differences are coupled to space encoding. Key questions: Does prompt optimization improve validity uniformly across models or do certain models perform better with specific prompt designs? Do encoding strategies (coordinate lists vs. ASCII grids vs. structured data objects) affect spatial reasoning performance?

Validation Studies

Expert validation addresses the circular reasoning limitation identified in Chapter 5. Practicing architects should review the constraint configuration for realism and completeness, evaluate generated layouts for architectural acceptability, and establish human performance baselines on the identical task.

6.3.2 Scaling Complexity

The evaluation tested a fixed constraint set on a 15×15 grid. Scaling along multiple dimensions would characterize capability boundaries:

Grid size Larger grids (20×20, 30×30) increase the solution space. Does validity degrade and to which degree does model performance scale?

Constraint count Adding constraints increases optimization difficulty. What is the relationship between constraint density and validity?

Multi-storey designs Vertical relationships between floors with stair alignment or shaft alignment introduce a third dimension of spatial reasoning. Can models maintain coherence across multiple stacked grids?

Constraint interactions More complex constraint types with interdependencies (e.g., if space A is adjacent to facade, then space B must not be) test logical reasoning in conjunction with spatial placement.

6.3.3 Domain Integration

The evaluation used abstract constraints disconnected from real-world architectural practice. Integration with domain knowledge would test generalization:

Structural systems Column grids, load-bearing walls, and shear cores impose geometric constraints. Can models reason about structural feasibility alongside spatial requirements?

Site context Real site boundaries, orientations, and access points. Can models reason about irregular geometries and contextual constraints like view axes, noise or solar exposure?

Regulatory compliance Building codes, zoning requirements, accessibility standards. These introduce hard constraints with legal implications.

Facade design Integration of window placement, daylight requirements, and exterior expression. Facade constraints link interior layout to building envelope.

Energy and sustainability Thermal zoning, natural ventilation potential, embodied carbon considerations. Performance constraints require reasoning about physical phenomena, not just spatial relationships.

6.3.4 Representation Extensions

The evaluation allocated programmatic spaces (“office,” “meeting room”) without interior detail. Richer representations would support more complete design automation:

Furnished space modules Pre-configured furniture layouts for common space types. Allocation becomes selection and placement of detailed modules rather than abstract zones.

Parametric spaces Spaces with adjustable properties (desk count, seating capacity) that constrain minimum dimensions. The model must reason about program requirements and their geometric implications.

6.3.5 Interface and Interaction

Practical deployment requires user-facing tools:

Specification interface Visual or conversational tools for constraint configuration. Users should be able to define requirements without writing YAML or understanding the underlying constraint schema.

Generation interface Controls for model selection for different parts of the workflow, parameter adjustment, and batch generation and comparisons. Integration with the validation framework for immediate feedback.

Result inspection Visualization of generated layouts with constraint satisfaction overlays. Comparison views for multiple candidates. Annotation tools for refinement requests.

XR interaction Immersive inspection of generated designs at architectural scale. Users could walk through layouts, identify spatial issues not apparent in plan view, and provide feedback through gestural or verbal input.

Collaborative specification Multi-user design sessions where stakeholders contribute constraints from different perspectives (client requirements, engineering constraints, aesthetic preferences). The system aggregates and validates for consistency before generation. Where the system would act as a mediator with the goal of reconciling conflicting requirements into a coherent design brief.

6.3.6 Cultural and Aesthetic Knowledge

Beyond functional constraints, layout generation could probe what spatial-cultural knowledge LLMs encode. Instructing models to generate designs reflecting specific

architectural traditions (Baroque axial symmetry, Modernist open plans, feng shui principles, or Japanese spatial hierarchies) would reveal whether training corpora embed distinct spatial logics or default to homogenized patterns potentially biased toward Western conventions. Similarly, abstract aesthetic concepts like harmony, proportion, or beauty could be specified as design objectives. Unlike functional constraints, such properties resist straightforward computational encoding: what constitutes “harmonious” space is culturally contingent and often tacit. Validation would therefore shift from automated constraint checking to human evaluation by experts or cultural informants. The generation infrastructure demonstrated in this thesis remains applicable, only the validation method changes. This direction connects to broader questions about cultural representation in AI systems, though systematic investigation remains future work.

6.4 Closing Remarks

The finding that frontier LLMs can create layouts that adhere to user specifications is within a narrow scope but consequential for research direction. It shows that natural language specification of spatial constraints is technically feasible with current LLMs.

This feasibility does not imply readiness for practice. Nevertheless the research directions outlined above are all very much tractable future investigations rather than speculation. The validation framework developed for this evaluation provides infrastructure for continued research. Any generation method (LLM, algorithmic, diffusion or hybrids) can be assessed against the same constraint set with the same metrics as long as a translation layer the output modalities can be. As models rapidly improve, this framework enables systematic comparison over time.

While this work has been primarily technical and mostly focused on LLM capabilities and the technicalities entailed by working with this technology, the broader vision remains. The path towards it is in fact clearer: Language models can become part of designing the spaces we inhabit. They currently can to a degree understand and reason about space planning problems. This certainly requires further interdisciplinary research that should at best include a broad range of expertise from architects, engineers, social and cognitive scientists to ensure that the technology is developed and integrated in a way that is useful, usable and ultimately beneficial to the world all living beings share. In times of increasing global tension, of climate change, war, of genocide and the destruction of the livelihoods of entire peoples, we will hopefully arrive at a point where that what has been destroyed will be rebuilt. This will require the construction of buildings and infrastructure on a scale my generation has not seen before. If AI can help us in doing so more sustainably, more efficiently and more democratically, perhaps our world will be at least a little better off than it is today.

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Appendix A

Experimental Prompt

This appendix contains the complete prompt used in the experiment. The prompt is structured to guide LLMs through the spatial design task while providing clear instructions for constraint satisfaction and output formatting.

```
1
2 You are an expert architectural designer. You are tasked with creating a
  ↳ spatial allocation plan, including door placements, for a building
  ↳ being designed on a grid.
3
4 ## General Instructions
5
6 - When creating spaces, pay attention to the dimensions of the resulting
  ↳ spaces. Make sure to create spaces that have the necessary size for
  ↳ their function.
7 - Be sensible about which spaces to place near the facade for natural light
  ↳ (e.g., work areas, lounge).
8 - Pay attention to the adjacencies of spaces and which spaces should
  ↳ logically be close to each other, following architectural best
  ↳ practices (e.g., kitchen near the lounge, bathrooms in a less central
  ↳ area).
9
10 ## Grid Information
11
12 - We have a 15x15 grid.
13 - Each cell is a square of 1.0x1.0 meters.
14 - Each grid cell is named as row;column (e.g., 0;0, 0;1, 0;2, etc.).
15 - We start counting from the top left corner of the grid, with the top row
  ↳ being row 0 and the left column being column 0.
16
17 ## Required Spaces to Allocate
18
19 - Open Work Area
20 - Meeting Room (2)
```

- 21 - Phone Booth (3)
- 22 - Kitchen
- 23 - Lounge
- 24 - Bathroom Women
- 25 - Bathroom Men
- 26 - Storage
- 27 - Reception
- 28 - Circulation(s)

29

30 ## Connectivity & Adjacency Requirements

31 Use the JSON structure below to define the required connections between
 ↪ spaces. This single source of truth governs both adjacency (physical
 ↪ boundaries) and access (doors).

32 Access Type door: This is a mandatory connection. It implies that the two
 ↪ spaces must be adjacent and there must be at least one door placed on
 ↪ their shared boundary. This is the primary way to ensure access.

33 Access Type adjacent: The spaces must share a physical boundary, but there
 ↪ should be no door between them. This is for relationships requiring
 ↪ proximity without direct access (e.g., for visual connection or
 ↪ functional grouping).

34 Access Type avoid: The spaces must not share a physical boundary. They
 ↪ should be separated by at least one intermediary space.

35 Default Rule: With the exception of the explicit connections defined below,
 ↪ no two functional spaces (e.g., Meeting Room to Bathroom) should have a
 ↪ door connection. All primary access should route through Circulation.

36

```

37 "connectivity_requirements": {
38   "spaces": [
39     {
40       "name": "Reception",
41       "connections": [
42         ["Circulation", "door"]
43       ]
44     },
45     {
46       "name": "Open Work Area",
47       "connections": [
48         ["Circulation", "door"],
49         ["Meeting Room", "adjacent"],
50         ["Bathroom Men", "avoid"],
51         ["Bathroom Women", "avoid"]
52       ]
53     },
54     {
55       "name": "Meeting Room",
56       "connections": [
57         ["Circulation", "door"],

```

```
58     ["Open Work Area","adjacent"]
59   ]
60 },
61 {
62   "name": "Phone Booth",
63   "connections": [
64     ["Circulation", "door"]
65   ]
66 },
67 {
68   "name": "Kitchen",
69   "connections": [
70     ["Lounge",      "door"],
71     ["Circulation", "door"]
72   ]
73 },
74 {
75   "name": "Lounge",
76   "connections": [
77     ["Kitchen",      "door"],
78     ["Circulation", "door"]
79   ]
80 },
81 {
82   "name": "Bathroom Men",
83   "connections": [
84     ["Bathroom Women", "adjacent"],
85     ["Circulation",   "door"],
86     ["Open Work Area","avoid"]
87   ]
88 },
89 {
90   "name": "Bathroom Women",
91   "connections": [
92     ["Bathroom Men", "adjacent"],
93     ["Circulation",   "door"],
94     ["Open Work Area","avoid"]
95   ]
96 },
97 {
98   "name": "Storage",
99   "connections": [
100     ["Circulation", "door"]
101   ]
102 }
103 ]
104 }
```

105

106 ## Constraints

107

- 108 - All spaces must be contiguous (their cells must be connected by shared
↪ edges).
- 109 - Each grid cell can only be allocated to one space.
- 110 - All 225 cells must be allocated to a space.
- 111 - Circulation space(s) must connect different areas efficiently and provide
↪ at least one access point to the facade.
- 112 - Circulation spaces must at no point be narrower than 2 meters (2 cells).
- 113 - All spaces must be made accessible by placing at least one door.

114

115 ## Output Format

116

117 Please provide your complete plan as a single JSON object. Make sure to
↪ allocate ALL 225 cells. The object should have the following structure:

118

```
119 {
120   "response": {
121     "reasoning": "A brief explanation of your allocation and door
↪ placement decisions, referencing architectural principles.",
122     "allocation": [
123       {
124         "space_id": "reception_1",
125         "name": "Reception",
126         "type": "reception",
127         "cell_ids": ["0;0", "0;1", "1;0", "1;1"]
128       },
129       {
130         "space_id": "circulation_1",
131         "name": "Circulation",
132         "type": "circulation",
133         "cell_ids": ["2;0", "2;1"]
134       }
135     ],
136     "doors": [
137       {
138         "reasoning": "Provides main entry access from circulation to
↪ reception area, essential for building wayfinding and
↪ security control.",
139         "source_space_id": "circulation_1",
140         "target_space_id": "reception_1",
141         "source_cell_id": "2;0",
142         "target_cell_id": "1;0"
143       },
144       {
145         "reasoning": "Connects circulation to open work area, allowing
↪ efficient movement of staff throughout the workspace.",
146
```

```
147         "source_space_id": "circulation_1",
148         "target_space_id": "open_work_area_1",
149         "source_cell_id": "2;1",
150         "target_cell_id": "1;1"
151     }
152     ...
153 ]
154 }
155 }
```

Appendix B

Constraint Configuration

This appendix contains the complete configuration file used to define spatial constraints in the experiment. It specifies the grid dimensions, space definitions with per-space constraints, and connectivity rules governing the spatial relationships between spaces.

```
1  grid:
2    width: 15
3    height: 15
4
5  spaces:
6    open_work_area_1:
7      contiguous: true
8
9    meeting_1:
10     contiguous: true
11
12   meeting_2:
13     contiguous: true
14
15   phone_booth_1:
16     contiguous: true
17
18   phone_booth_2:
19     contiguous: true
20
21   phone_booth_3:
22     contiguous: true
23
24   kitchen_1:
25     contiguous: true
26
27   lounge_1:
28     contiguous: true
29
```

```
30 bathroom_women_1:
31     contiguous: true
32
33 bathroom_men_1:
34     contiguous: true
35
36 storage_1:
37     contiguous: true
38
39 reception_1:
40     contiguous: true
41
42 circulation_1:
43     min_width: 2
44     facade_access: required
45     contiguous: false
46
47 connectivity:
48     # Reception
49     - reception_1 door_to circulation_1
50
51     # Open Work Area
52     - open_work_area_1 door_to circulation_1
53     - open_work_area_1 adjacent_to meeting_1
54     - open_work_area_1 adjacent_to meeting_2
55     - open_work_area_1 avoid bathroom_men_1
56     - open_work_area_1 avoid bathroom_women_1
57
58     # Meeting Rooms (each needs door to circulation)
59     - meeting_1 door_to circulation_1
60     - meeting_2 door_to circulation_1
61
62     # Phone Booths (each needs door to circulation)
63     - phone_booth_1 door_to circulation_1
64     - phone_booth_2 door_to circulation_1
65     - phone_booth_3 door_to circulation_1
66
67     # Kitchen & Lounge
68     - kitchen_1 door_to lounge_1
69     - kitchen_1 door_to circulation_1
70     - lounge_1 door_to circulation_1
71
72     # Bathrooms
73     - bathroom_men_1 adjacent_to bathroom_women_1
74     - bathroom_men_1 door_to circulation_1
75     - bathroom_women_1 door_to circulation_1
76
77     - storage_1 door_to circulation_1
```

Appendix C

Constraint Validation System

This appendix documents the constraint validation framework referenced in Chapter 3. The system evaluates LLM-generated layouts against spatial requirements using a strategy pattern where each constraint type is implemented as a separate module.

C.1 Evaluation System Architecture

The validation framework separates constraint logic from geometric operations through two abstractions:

Constraint Interface: Each constraint implements a common interface with an `evaluate()` method that yields binary pass/fail results with diagnostic metadata.

Geometry Engine: A `GridGeometry` class encapsulates all geometric operations (adjacency detection, contiguity checking, facade access) using pure Python with `NetworkX` for graph operations.

The `EvaluationRunner` orchestrates the pipeline: loading responses, building topological representations, dispatching to constraint modules, and aggregating results. Figure C.1 shows the complete evaluation flow.

C.2 Core Interfaces

The constraint system uses Python's abstract base class pattern. All constraints inherit from a base class defining the evaluation signature:

```
class Constraint(ABC):  
    constraint_type: str
```


Figure C.1
Evaluation pipeline from JSON input to aggregated results.

```

@abstractmethod
def evaluate(
    self,
    geometry: GeometryEngine,
    space_shells: dict[str, GridSpace],
    grid_shell: GridSpace,
    doors: list[dict[str, str | None]],
    config: EvalConfig,
) -> Iterator[ConstraintResult]: ...

```

Each constraint yields one or more `ConstraintResult` objects:

```

@dataclass
class ConstraintResult:
    constraint_id: str # e.g., "presence_kitchen_1"
    constraint_type: str # e.g., "presence"
    passed: bool
    skipped: bool # True if prerequisite failed
    metadata: dict[str, Any] # Diagnostic info

```

The `GridGeometry` engine provides spatial operations:

```

class GridGeometry:
    def get_cell_count(self, shell: GridSpace) -> int
    def check_contiguous(self, shell: GridSpace) -> bool
    def check_adjacent(self, s1: GridSpace, s2: GridSpace) -> bool
    def check_facade_access(self, shell: GridSpace, grid: GridSpace) ->
        ↪ bool
    def get_rectangularity(self, shell: GridSpace) -> float
    def has_bottleneck(self, shell: GridSpace) -> bool
    def build_connectivity_graph(
        self,
        shells: dict[str, GridSpace],
        doors: list[dict]
    ) -> tuple[bool, int] # (is_connected, component_count)

```

C.3 Constraint Catalog

The framework implements eleven constraint types organized by scope. Tables C.1–C.3 summarize each constraint’s purpose and primary validation method.

C.3.1 Space Constraints

Space constraints validate properties of individual allocated spaces.

Table C.1*Space constraint types validating individual spaces.*

Constraint	Purpose	Key Method
Presence	Space instance exists in allocation	Dictionary key lookup
Area	Cell count within configured bounds	<code>get_cell_count()</code>
Contiguity	All cells form single connected region	<code>check_contiguous()</code>
Min Width	No 1-cell-wide bottlenecks	<code>has_bottleneck()</code>
Facade Access	At least one cell on grid perimeter	<code>check_facade_access()</code>
Shape	Rectangularity ratio \geq threshold	<code>get_rectangularity()</code>

C.3.2 Connectivity Constraints

Connectivity constraints validate relationships between pairs or groups of spaces.

Table C.2*Connectivity constraint types validating spatial relationships.*

Constraint	Purpose	Key Method
Adjacency	Two spaces share at least one edge	<code>check_adjacent()</code>
Door	Door connection between adjacent spaces	<code>check_adjacent()</code> + door list
Avoidance	Two spaces do NOT share any edge	not <code>check_adjacent()</code>
Global Connectivity	All spaces reachable via doors	<code>build_connectivity_graph()</code>

C.3.3 Layout Constraints

Layout constraints validate properties of the overall grid allocation.

Table C.3*Layout constraint types validating overall allocation.*

Constraint	Purpose	Key Method
Grid Bounds	All cells within grid dimensions	Coordinate range check
Cell Overlap	No cell assigned to multiple spaces	Set deduplication
Allocation	Total cells match target (e.g., 100%)	Cell union counting

C.4 Grid-Based Geometric Operations

The `GridGeometry` engine implements spatial operations using 4-connectivity on the discrete grid. Key algorithms:

4-Connectivity. Two cells are adjacent if their Manhattan distance equals 1 (sharing an edge, not just a corner). For cells (r_1, c_1) and (r_2, c_2) : adjacent iff $|r_1 - r_2| + |c_1 - c_2| = 1$.

Contiguity Check. Breadth-first search from any cell in the space. The space is contiguous if all cells are visited in a single traversal. Implementation uses `NetworkX.is_connected()` on the cell adjacency graph.

Bottleneck Detection. Articulation points in the cell adjacency graph indicate 1-cell-wide sections. A cell is an articulation point if its removal disconnects the graph. Implementation uses `NetworkX.articulation_points()`.

Facade Access. A space has facade access if any cell lies on the grid boundary: $\text{row} \in \{0, \text{rows} - 1\}$ or $\text{column} \in \{0, \text{cols} - 1\}$.

Rectangularity. Ratio of actual cell count to bounding box area: $\text{rectangularity} = \frac{|\text{cells}|}{(r_{\max} - r_{\min} + 1) \times (c_{\max} - c_{\min} + 1)}$. A value of 1.0 indicates a perfect rectangle.

Adjacency Between Spaces. Two spaces are adjacent if any cell in one space is 4-adjacent to any cell in the other. Implementation iterates over boundary cells for efficiency.

Global Connectivity Graph. A space-level graph where nodes represent spaces and edges represent door connections. BFS determines if all spaces are reachable from any starting node. Returns the number of connected components (1 = fully connected).

C.5 Computational Complexity

For a grid of N total cells with S spaces:

- **Contiguity:** $O(n)$ per space, where n is the space's cell count
- **Bottleneck detection:** $O(n)$ using Tarjan's algorithm via `NetworkX`
- **Adjacency:** $O(b_1 + b_2)$ where b_i is boundary cell count

- **Global connectivity:** $O(S + D)$ where D is door count
- **Full evaluation:** $O(N + S^2)$ worst case, typically $O(N)$ for sparse connectivity

Appendix D

Evaluated Constraints

Table D.1 presents the complete list of 49 constraints evaluated for each generated layout. These constraints are instantiated from the configuration in Appendix B, with space-specific constraints generated for each required space instance.

Table D.1

Complete list of evaluated constraints in the grid-based layout generation task.

Category	Constraint
Structural	grid_bounds
	cell_overlap
	allocation
	global_connectivity
Open Work Area	presence_open_work_area_1
	contiguity_open_work_area_1
Meeting Rooms	presence_meeting_1
	contiguity_meeting_1
	presence_meeting_2
	contiguity_meeting_2
Phone Booths	presence_phone_booth_1
	contiguity_phone_booth_1
	presence_phone_booth_2
	contiguity_phone_booth_2
	presence_phone_booth_3
contiguity_phone_booth_3	
Kitchen	presence_kitchen_1
	contiguity_kitchen_1

Continued on next page

Category	Constraint
Lounge	presence_lounge_1 contiguity_lounge_1
Bathrooms	presence_bathroom_women_1 contiguity_bathroom_women_1 presence_bathroom_men_1 contiguity_bathroom_men_1
Storage	presence_storage_1 contiguity_storage_1
Reception	presence_reception_1 contiguity_reception_1
Circulation	presence_circulation_1 facade_circulation_1 min_width_circulation_1
Door Connections	door_reception_1_circulation_1 door_open_work_area_1_circulation_1 door_meeting_1_circulation_1 door_meeting_2_circulation_1 door_phone_booth_1_circulation_1 door_phone_booth_2_circulation_1 door_phone_booth_3_circulation_1 door_kitchen_1_lounge_1 door_kitchen_1_circulation_1 door_lounge_1_circulation_1 door_bathroom_men_1_circulation_1 door_bathroom_women_1_circulation_1 door_storage_1_circulation_1
Adjacency	adjacency_open_work_area_1_meeting_1 adjacency_open_work_area_1_meeting_2 adjacency_bathroom_men_1_bathroom_women_1
Avoidance	avoidance_open_work_area_1_bathroom_men_1 avoidance_open_work_area_1_bathroom_women_1